

JavaScript Scripts for Capturing and Python Scripts for Processing Client-Based Paradata in Web Surveys

Authors: Nejc Berzelak, Peter Hrvatin, and Vasja Vehovar

*Centre for Social Informatics, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, Kardeljeva
ploščad 5, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

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1 JavaScript Scripts for Capturing Paradata

1.1 Advanced paradata

```
// The main function that is always called for logging
function logEvent(event_type, event, data){

    //console.log(event_type + ' ' + event + ' ' + _session_id);

    // We get the session id on the page
    var session_id = _session_id;

    // We get the survey id
    var anketa = $('#srv_meta_anketa_id').val();

    // We get the current page
    if (typeof srv_meta_grupa_id != 'undefined'){
        var page = srv_meta_grupa_id;
    }
    else if ($('#outercontainer').hasClass('intro')){
        var page = '-1';
    }
    else if ($('#outercontainer').hasClass('concl')){
        var page = '-2';
    }
    else{
        var page = '0';
    }

    // We get user id, recnum and language
    var user = _usr_id;
    var recnum = _recnum;
    var language = _lang;

    // We note the time of the event
    var timestamp = Date.now();

    // Optional parameter data
    data = data || '';

    // In the submit or unload event, the call must be synchronous
    if(event == 'unload_page'){
        $.ajax({
            type: 'POST',
            url: '../main/survey/ajax.php?t=parapodatki&a=logData',
            data: {
                session_id: session_id,
                anketa: anketa,
                page: page,
                usr_id: user,
                recnum: recnum,
                language: language,

                event_type: event_type,
                event: event,
                timestamp: timestamp,

                data: data
            },
            /*success: success,
            dataType: dataType,*/
            async: false
        });
    }
    else{
        $.post('../main/survey/ajax.php?t=parapodatki&a=logData', {
            session_id: session_id,
            anketa: anketa,
            page: page,
            usr_id: user,
            recnum: recnum,
            language: language,
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        event_type: event_type,
        event: event,
        timestamp: timestamp,

        data: data
    });
}
}

// Events that we monitor
$(function () {

    // LOAD PAGE
    window.addEventListener('load', function () {

        var event_type = 'page';
        var event = 'load_page';

        // We monitor parameters for size and zoom
        var data = {
            devicePixelRatio: window.devicePixelRatio,
            width: window.screen.width,
            height: window.screen.height,
            availWidth: window.screen.availWidth,
            availHeight: window.screen.availHeight,
            jquery_windowW: $(window).width(),
            jquery_windowH: $(window).height(),
            jquery_documentW: $(document).width(),
            jquery_documentH: $(document).height(),
        }

        // We log load
        logEvent(event_type, event, data);

        // We log visible questions
        //visibleQuestions();
    });

    // RESIZE
    window.addEventListener('resize', function () {

        var data = {
            pos_x: $(window).width(),
            pos_y: $(window).height(),
            value: window.devicePixelRatio
        }

        var event_type = 'other';
        var event = 'resize';

        // We log scroll
        logEvent(event_type, event, data);

        // We log visible questions
        //visibleQuestions();
    });

    // PINCH ZOOM
    var pinch_scaling = false;
    var pinch_distance = 0;
    window.addEventListener('touchstart', function (e) {

        // We detect two fingers
        if (e.touches.length === 2) {
            pinch_scaling = true;

            // We calculate the distance between fingers
            pinch_distance = Math.hypot(
                e.touches[0].screenX - e.touches[1].screenX,
                e.touches[0].screenY - e.touches[1].screenY
            );
        }
    });
    window.addEventListener('touchend', function (e) {

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    if(pinch_scaling){
        pinch_scaling = false;

        // Izracunamo razdaljo med prstoma
        var pinch_distance2 = Math.hypot(
            e.touches[0].screenX - e.changedTouches[0].screenX,
            e.touches[0].screenY - e.changedTouches[0].screenY
        );

        // We calculate the difference in distance
        var diff = pinch_distance2 - pinch_distance;
        var zoom = Math.round((diff / pinch_distance * 100));

        var data = {
            value: zoom
        }

        var event_type = 'other';
        var event = 'pinch_resize';

        // We log scroll
        logEvent(event_type, event, data);
    }
});

// ORIENTATION CHANGE
window.addEventListener('orientationchange', function () {

    var value = '';

    if(window.orientation == 90 || window.orientation == -90)
        value = 'landscape';
    else
        value = 'portrait';

        var data = {
            value: value
        }

        var event_type = 'other';
        var event = 'orientation_change';

        // We log scroll
        logEvent(event_type, event, data);
});

// SCROLL
var scroll_time_prev = 0;
window.addEventListener('scroll', function () {

    // We get the current time
    var scroll_time = new Date().getTime();

    // If enough time has passed since the previous detection
    if ((scroll_time - scroll_time_prev > 50) || scroll_time_prev == 0) {

        var event_type = 'other';
        var event = 'scroll_page';

        var data = {
            pos_x: (window.pageXOffset || document.documentElement.scrollLeft) -
(document.documentElement.clientLeft || 0),
            pos_y: (window.pageYOffset || document.documentElement.scrollTop) -
(document.documentElement.clientTop || 0)
        }

        // We log scroll
        logEvent(event_type, event, data);

        // We log visible questions
        //visibleQuestions();

        // We save the time for the interval
        scroll_time_prev = scroll_time;
    }
});

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    });

// BLUR (leave to another tab etc..)
window.addEventListener('blur', function () {

    var event_type = 'other';
    var event = 'blur';

    logEvent(event_type, event);
});

// FOCUS
window.addEventListener('focus', function () {

    var event_type = 'other';
    var event = 'focus';

    logEvent(event_type, event);
});

// MOUSE CLICK
window.addEventListener('click', function (event) {

    var div_id = $(event.target).attr('id');

    // If the id is empty, we find the first parent with the id
    if(div_id == null){
        div_id = $(event.target).closest('[id]').attr('id') + ' (parent)';
    }

    var data = {
        pos_x: event.pageX,
        pos_y: event.pageY,
        div_type: event.target.tagName,
        div_id: div_id,
        div_class: $(event.target).attr('class')
    }

    var event_type = 'other';
    var event_name = 'click';

    logEvent(event_type, event_name, data);

    // We specifically save the mouse movement until this click
    movementClickEvent(event);
});

// INPUT TEXT, TEXTAREA FOCUS
$('input[type=text], textarea').bind('focus', function () {

    // If it is a textbox in the select, it is ignored
    if(!$(this).parent().hasClass('chzn-search')){

        var event_type = 'vrednost';
        var event = 'text_enter';

        var id = $(this).attr('id');
        var id_array = id.split('_');
        var spr_id = id_array[1];
        var vre_id = id_array[3];

        var data = {
            spr_id: spr_id,
            vre_id: vre_id,
            value: $(this).val()
        }

        logEvent(event_type, event, data);

        // Let's check if it's another field - then mark the checkbox/radio as well
        if($(this).parent().parent().parent().hasClass('tip_1') ||
        $(this).parent().parent().parent().hasClass('tip_2')){

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        event = 'radio_checkbox_change';

        data = {
            spr_id: spr_id,
            vre_id: vre_id,
            value: 1
        }

        logEvent(event_type, event, data);
    }
}

});
// INPUT TEXT, TEXTAREA BLUR
$('input[type=text], textarea').bind('blur', function () {

    // If it is a textbox in the select, it is ignored
    if(!$(this).parent().hasClass('chzn-search')){

        var event_type = 'vrednost';
        var event = 'text_leave';

        var id = $(this).attr('id');
        var id_array = id.split('_');
        var spr_id = id_array[1];
        var vre_id = id_array[3];

        var data = {
            spr_id: spr_id,
            vre_id: vre_id,
            value: $(this).val()
        }

        logEvent(event_type, event, data);
    }
});

// INPUT RADIO, CHECKBOX CHANGE
$('input[type=radio], input[type=checkbox]').bind('click', function () {

    var event_type = 'vrednost';
    var event = 'radio_checkbox_change';

    var id = $(this).attr('id');
    var id_array = id.split('_');

    // If it's a table
    if(id_array[2] == 'grid' || id_array[0] == 'grid'){
        var spr_id = id_array[1];
        var vre_id = id_array[3];

        // If it is 'value', it is missing
        if(spr_id == 'missing'){
            spr_id = id_array[3];
            vre_id = id_array[5];
        }
    }
    // Ordinary radio or checkbox
    else{
        var spr_id = id_array[1];
        var vre_id = id_array[3];

        // If it is 'value', it is missing
        if(spr_id == 'value'){
            spr_id = id_array[3];
            vre_id = id_array[5];
        }
    }

    var val;
    if ($(this).is(':checked'))
        val = 1;
    else
        val = 0

    var data = {

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        spr_id: spr_id,
        vre_id: vre_id,
        value: val
    }

    logEvent(event_type, event, data);
});

// SELECT CHANGE
$('select').bind('change', function () {

    var event_type = 'vrednost';
    var event = 'select_change';

    var id = $(this).attr('id');
    var id_array = id.split('_');
    var spr_id = id_array[1];
    var vre_id = $(this).val();

    var data = {
        spr_id: spr_id,
        vre_id: vre_id,
        value: vre_id
    }

    logEvent(event_type, event, data);
});

// MOUSE MOVE
var movements = [];
var currentMovement = {
    timeStart: 0,
    timeEnd: 0,
    duration: 0,

    startPosX: 0,
    startPosY: 0,
    endPosX: 0,
    endPosY: 0,

    distance_traveled: 0,
    prevPosX: 0,
    prevPosY: 0
}

// We capture all mouse movements
window.addEventListener('mousemove', function (event) {
    var clicked = false;
    movementTrack(event, clicked);
});

// We record the movement in the array of objects
var time_prev = new Date().getTime();
function movementTrack(event, clicked){

    // We get the current time
    var time = new Date().getTime();

    // If enough time has passed since the previous detection
    if (time - time_prev > 50 || clicked) {

        // Let's check if this is already a new movement - for now we treat a new movement
        // if the pause is more than 300ms
        if(time - currentMovement.timeEnd > 300 || clicked){

            // We add the current movement to the movements array - the trick is not to
            // insert a reference but an actual copy of the object
            if(currentMovement.timeStart !== 0 && currentMovement.startPosX !== undefined
            && currentMovement.endPosX !== undefined){
                movements.push(JSON.parse(JSON.stringify(currentMovement)));
            }

            // We reset the current movement and set all its parameters
            currentMovement.timeStart = time;

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        currentMovement.timeEnd = time;

        currentMovement.startPosX = event.pageX;
        currentMovement.startPosY = event.pageY;

        currentMovement.endPosX = event.pageX;
        currentMovement.endPosY = event.pageY;

        currentMovement.distance_traveled = 0;
        currentMovement.prevPosX = event.pageX;
        currentMovement.prevPosY = event.pageY;
    }
    // It's an old move - we just update the end time and end position
    else{
        currentMovement.timeEnd = time;
        currentMovement.duration = time - currentMovement.timeStart;

        currentMovement.endPosX = event.pageX;
        currentMovement.endPosY = event.pageY;

        // We calculate the distance traveled since the previous move
        var a = currentMovement.prevPosX - event.pageX;
        var b = currentMovement.prevPosY - event.pageY;
        var distance = Math.sqrt(a*a + b*b);

        currentMovement.distance_traveled += distance;
        currentMovement.prevPosX = event.pageX;
        currentMovement.prevPosY = event.pageY;
    }

    // Let's save the time for the interval
    time_prev = time;

    /*console.log(currentMovement);*/
}

// We call on every click and save data about the movement during the click
function movementClickEvent(event) {

    var event_type = 'movement';
    var event = 'mouse_move';

    var clicked = true;
    movementTrack(event, clicked);

    // Loop through all moves
    for (var i=0; i<movements.length; i++) {

        var data = {
            time_start: movements[i].timeStart,
            time_end: movements[i].timeEnd,
            pos_x_start: movements[i].startPosX,
            pos_y_start: movements[i].startPosY,
            pos_x_end: movements[i].endPosX,
            pos_y_end: movements[i].endPosY,
            distance: movements[i].distance_traveled
        }

        logEvent(event_type, event, data);
    }

    // Let's clear the array of all movements
    movements = [];
}

// VISIBLE
/*function visibleQuestions() {

    var event_type = 'other';
    var event = 'visible_question';

    var q = $('grupa').find('spremenljivka');
    var arr = [];
}

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$.each(q, function (i, val) {
    if ($(val).is(':visible') && isVisible(val)) {
        if ($(val).attr('id'))
            arr[arr.length] = $(val).attr('id').substring(14);
    }
})

var log = "" + arr;

if (log != prev_log) {
    var data = {
        log: log
    }

    logEvent(event_type, event, data);

    prev_log = log;
}
}
var prev_log = '';

// We return if the element is visible
function isVisible(elem) {

    var containerTop = $(window).scrollTop();
    var containerBottom = containerTop + $(window).height();

    var elemTop = $(elem).offset().top;
    var elemBottom = elemTop + $(elem).height();

    return ((elemBottom >= containerTop) && (elemTop <= containerBottom)
    && (elemBottom <= containerBottom) && (elemTop >= containerTop) );
}*/
})

```

1.2 Post time

```

// EVENT LEAVE PAGE, which must be executed synchronously (otherwise it will be lost in some
browsers)
$(function () {

    // LEAVE PAGE (we look at unload, beforeunload, click on submit, click on back)
    var leavePageFunction_called = false;
    var leavePageFunction = function () {
        var event_type = 'page';
        var event = 'unload_page';

        if(!leavePageFunction_called){
            logEvent(event_type, event);
            leavePageFunction_called = true;
        }
    }
    window.addEventListener('beforeunload', leavePageFunction);
    window.addEventListener('unload', leavePageFunction);
    $("input.next:submit").bind('click', leavePageFunction);
    $("input.prev:button").bind('click', leavePageFunction);

})

```

1.3 Prompts

```

var spr_id_variable = []; // to track alerts: a field that holds the
spr_id where alerts occur
var tip_opozorila = []; // for alert tracking: a field that holds
the reminder/alert type
var spr_id_indeks = 0; // to track alerts: index to the
fields that hold the spr_id where the alerts occur and the reminder type
var opozorila_sum = []; // to track alerts
var opozorila_num = []; // to track alerts
var opozorila_validation = []; // to track alerts

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var tip_opozorila_temp = [];
var validacijaZabelezena = [];
var zacetnaValidacijaZabelezena = 1; // records if the validation was recorded, not
dynamically, without the respondent clicking on any answer and going directly to the next page
of the survey
var spremenljivkaVal = []; // a field that records which variables
have a wave warning

// WE DETECT THE TRIGGER OF THE ALERT
$(function () {

    var time_display;

    // remember the normal alert
    var oldAlert = (function(){ return this.alert; }()),
    oldConfirm = (function(){ return this.confirm; }());

    // inject ourself into the window.alert and window.confirm globals
    alert = function (msg) {
        time_display = Date.now();

        oldAlert.call(window, msg);
        window.onAlert(msg);
    };
    confirm = function (msg) {
        time_display = Date.now();

        var result = oldConfirm.call(window, msg);
        window.onConfirm(msg, result);

        return result;
    };

    // these just listen for events
    window.onAlert = function (text) {
        logAlert({text:text, type:'alert box', ignorable:0, action:'ok',
time_display:time_display});
    };
    window.onConfirm = function (text, result) {
        var action = result ? 'yes' : 'no';
        logAlert({text:text, type:'confirm box', ignorable:1, action:action,
time_display:time_display});
    };
});

// We log an alert (upon submission)
function logAlert(box_data){

    //console.log("Trenutna dolzina polja: "+spr_id_variable.length);
    //console.log(box_data);

    var spremenljivkaVal = []; // a field that stores the spr_id of variables with a
triggered val warning
    var tip_opozorila_tmp = [];

    spr_id_variable.forEach(function(variable, index) {

        // if the warning type contains a comma, it means that it records two warnings
at the same time
        // break the warning into two parts
        if(tip_opozorila[variable].includes(",")){
            var opozorilo = tip_opozorila[variable].split(",");
            opozorilo[1] = opozorilo[1].substring(1); // remove the space at the
beginning of the warning

            //$.post('../main/survey/ajax.php?t=parapodatki&a=logData', {usr_id:
_usr_id, what: opozorilo[0], what2: opozorilo[1], gru_id: page, anketa: srv_meta_anketa_id,
spr_id_variable: variable});
            var event_type = 'alert';
            var event = 'alert';

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        opozorilo_type[0] = opozorilo[0].substring(4);
        opozorilo_trigger_type[0] = opozorilo[0].substring(0, 3);
        opozorilo_type[1] = opozorilo[1].substring(4);
        opozorilo_trigger_type[1] = opozorilo[1].substring(0, 3);

        var data = {
            type: opozorilo_type[0] + ' ' + opozorilo_type[1] + ' (' +
box_data.type + ')',
            trigger_id: variable,
            trigger_type: opozorilo_trigger_type[0] + ' ' +
opozorilo_trigger_type[1],
            text: box_data.text,
            ignorable: box_data.ignorable,
            action: box_data.action,
            time_display: box_data.time_display
        };

        logEvent(event_type, event, data);
    }
    else{
        //$.post('../main/survey/ajax.php?t=parapodatki&a=logData', {usr_id:
_usr_id, what: tip_opozorila[variable], gru_id: page, anketa: srv_meta_anketa_id,
spr_id_variable: variable});
        var event_type = 'alert';
        var event = 'alert';

        var opozorilo_type = tip_opozorila[variable].substring(4);
        var opozorilo_trigger_type = tip_opozorila[variable].substring(0, 3);

        // If it is a multigrid, we only record the id of the question
        if(variable.substring(0, 12) == '#vrednost_if'){

            var spremenljivka_id =
$(""+variable).closest('.spremenljivka').attr('id').substring(14);

            //variable = spremenljivka_id + '_' + variable.substring(13);
            variable = spremenljivka_id;
        }

        var data = {
            type: opozorilo_type + ' (' + box_data.type + ')',
            trigger_id: variable,
            trigger_type: opozorilo_trigger_type,
            text: box_data.text,
            ignorable: box_data.ignorable,
            action: box_data.action,
            time_display: box_data.time_display
        };

        logEvent(event_type, event, data);
    }

    //console.log("Spr_id opozorila: "+variable+", indeks "+index+",
tip:"+tip_opozorila[variable]+" za user: "+_usr_id+" zacetnaValidacijaZabelezena:
"+zacetnaValidacijaZabelezena);

    // if no initial validation is recorded and the warning type is validation
    if(zacetnaValidacijaZabelezena == 0 && tip_opozorila[variable].includes("val"))
    {
        spremenljivkaVal.push(variable);

        // if a double warning is recorded
        if(tip_opozorila[variable].includes(",")){
            tip_opozorila_tmp[variable] = opozorilo[0];
        }
        else{
            tip_opozorila_tmp[variable] = tip_opozorila[variable];
        }
    }
}
});

spr_id_variable = []; // clearing the field
tip_opozorila = [];

if(spremenljivkaVal.length != 0){
    spremenljivkaVal.forEach(function(valSprem) {

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        spr_id_variable.push(valSprem);
        tip_opozorila[valSprem] = tip_opozorila_tmp[valSprem];
    });
}

//console.log("Polje spremenljivkaVal: "+spremenljivkaVal.length);
}

function dodaj_opozorilo_val(bol, id){

    var spr_id = id.replace('#spremenljivka_', '');

    //console.log("Tip opozorila prej:" + tip_opozorila[spr_id]);

    if(zacetnaValidacijaZabelezena == 1){
        zacetnaValidacijaZabelezena = 0;
    }
    else{
    }

    if(!validacijaZabelezena[spr_id]){
        spr_id_variable.push(spr_id);
    }

    var tip_alerta = '';

    tip_alerta = 'val';
    validacijaZabelezena[spr_id] = 1;
    spremenljivkaVal[spr_id] = spr_id;

    tip_opozorila[spr_id] = tip_alerta + ' ' + bol + ' alert';
}

function dodaj_opozorilo(alert_sum, alert_num, alert_validation, bol, id){

    //console.log("Dodaj opozorilo");

    var spr_id = id.replace('#spremenljivka_', '');

    var tip_alerta = '';

    if(alert_sum) tip_alerta = 'sum';
    if(alert_num) tip_alerta = 'num';

    if(tip_alerta == ''){

        // if no warning has been recorded for this variable
        if(tip_opozorila[spr_id] == undefined){
            tip_opozorila[spr_id] = bol+' alert';
            spr_id_variable.push(spr_id);
        }
        else{
            // otherwise, if some kind of warning is recorded, usually when there is
validation
            tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id] = bol+' alert';

            // if the previous warning is the same as the current one
            if(tip_opozorila[spr_id] == tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id]){

                tip_opozorila[spr_id] = tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id];
                tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id] = '';

                spr_id_variable.push(spr_id);
            }
            // otherwise, we have two different warnings that need to be noted
            else if(validacijaZabelezena[spr_id] == 1){

                tip_opozorila[spr_id] = tip_opozorila[spr_id]+' '+bol+' alert';
                tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id] = '';

                //console.log("Dvojno opozorilo");
            }
        }
    }
}

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    }
    else{
        // if no warning has been recorded for this variable
        if(tip_opozorila[spr_id] == undefined){

            tip_opozorila[spr_id] = tip_alerta+' '+bol+' alert';
            spr_id_variable.push(spr_id);
        }
        // otherwise, if some kind of warning is recorded, usually when there is
validation
        else{
            tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id] = tip_alerta+' '+bol+' alert';

            // if the previous warning is the same as the current one
            if(tip_opozorila[spr_id] == tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id]){
                tip_opozorila[spr_id] = tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id];
                tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id] = '';
                spr_id_variable.push(spr_id);
            }
            // otherwise, we have two different warnings that need to be noted
            else if(validacijaZabelezena[spr_id] == 1){
                tip_opozorila[spr_id] = tip_opozorila[spr_id]+' '+tip_alerta+'
'+bol+' alert';
                tip_opozorila_temp[spr_id] = '';
            }
        }
    }
}

function odstrani_opozorilo(id, alert_sum, alert_num, alert_validation){
    //console.log("Odstrani");

    var spr_id = id.replace('#spremenljivka_', '');

    tip_opozorila.splice(spr_id, 1);    // remove the warning from the field

    if(alert_validation){
        // remove the recorded validation from the field
        spr_id_variable.forEach(function(variable, index) {
            if(variable == spremljivkaVal[variable]){
                spr_id_variable.splice(index, 1);
            }
        });

        validacijaZabelezena[spr_id] = 0;
    }
}

```

2 Python Scripts for Processing Paradata

2.1 Metadata parser

```
def metadata_parse(file):
    import pandas as pd
    import numpy as np
    import json
    from pandas.io.json import json_normalize

    with open(file) as json_file:
        json_import = json.load(json_file)

    # Create multiple dataframes to store relevant information at different levels.
    Workarounds by parsing individual
    # dataframe columns containing lower-level JSON tags is used due to problems handling non-
    existant tags.
    # TODO: Make more efficient (e.g. without loops where possible)

    # Parse and edit metadata at the level of pages.
    pages = json_normalize(json_import, record_path=['survey', 'questionnaire', 'pages'],
                           meta=[["survey", "id"]]).copy()
    pages.rename(columns={"id": "page_id", "survey.id": "survey_id"}, inplace=True)

    # Get questions from pages and remove questions metadata from the pages dataframe
    questions_json = pages[pages["questions"].isnull() == False][["survey_id", "page_id",
"questions"]]
    pages.drop(columns="questions", inplace=True)

    # Parse and edit metadata at the level of questions. Higher level identifiers are kept for
    easier handling.
    questions = pd.DataFrame(columns=["survey_id", "page_id"])
    for i_row in range(0, questions_json.shape[0]):
        i_row_questions = json_normalize(questions_json.iloc[i_row, 2])
        i_row_questions = i_row_questions.assign(survey_id=questions_json.iloc[i_row, 0],
                                                page_id=questions_json.iloc[i_row, 1])
        questions = questions.append(i_row_questions, sort=False, ignore_index=True)
    questions.rename(columns={"id": "question_id"}, inplace=True)
    questions[["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id"]] = questions[["survey_id", "page_id",
"question_id"]].astype(
        np.int64)

    # Get items and response options from questions and remove these columns from the
    questions dataframe.
    items_json = questions[questions["items"].isnull() == False][
        ["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id", "items"]].copy()
    response_options_json = questions[questions["answers"].isnull() == False][
        ["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id", "answers"]].copy()
    questions.drop(columns=["items", "answers"], inplace=True)

    items = pd.DataFrame(columns=["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id"])
    for i_row in range(0, items_json.shape[0]):
        i_row_items = json_normalize(items_json.iloc[i_row, 3])
        i_row_items = i_row_items.assign(survey_id=items_json.iloc[i_row, 0],
                                        page_id=items_json.iloc[i_row, 1],
                                        question_id=items_json.iloc[i_row, 2])
        items = items.append(i_row_items, sort=False, ignore_index=True)
    items.rename(columns={"id": "item_id"}, inplace=True)
    items[["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id", "item_id"]] = items[
        ["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id", "item_id"]].astype(np.int64)

    response_options = pd.DataFrame(columns=["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id"])
    for i_row in range(0, response_options_json.shape[0]):
        i_row_response_options = json_normalize(response_options_json.iloc[i_row, 3])
        i_row_response_options =
    i_row_response_options.assign(survey_id=response_options_json.iloc[i_row, 0],
    page_id=response_options_json.iloc[i_row, 1],
    question_id=response_options_json.iloc[i_row, 2])
        response_options = response_options.append(i_row_response_options, sort=False,
ignore_index=True)
    response_options.rename(columns={"id": "response_option_id"}, inplace=True)
```

```

    response_options[["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id", "response_option_id"]] =
response_options[
    ["survey_id", "page_id", "question_id", "response_option_id"]].astype(np.int64)

    # Store everything in a dictionary and return it.
    questionnaire_spec = {"pages": pages, "questions": questions, "items": items,
"response_options": response_options}
    return questionnaire_spec

```

2.2 Paradata import

```

# PARADATA IMPORT
# This code imports paradata from raw files exported from lKA.

# A majority of merging and linking between datafiles is not performed at this stage. The
exception include merging some
# information from the questionnaire metadata and pre-requirements for data cleaning and
handling of missing values
# at later stages.

# It is probably good idea to define function to import each paradata type. This is not done
in this script but should
# be quite easy to do. In this case, processing settings should be defined at the level of
individual functions.
# This file needs to be run second, after metadata parser. Code contained in other files
assume existance of some objects
# created by this code.

import pandas as pd
import numpy as np

# Define variables to store different types of paradata, settings and processing logs.
settings = {}
paradata_raw = {}
ref_data = {}
processing_log = []

# Source parameters.
settings["data_folder"] = "/Users/nejc/OneDrive - Univerza v Ljubljani/RR Projekti/2018
Paradata TP BL/Survey/Paradata/Raw/Paradata export SI rev0-NB/"
settings["metadata_file"] = "/Users/nejc/OneDrive - Univerza v Ljubljani/RR Projekti/2018
Paradata TP BL/Survey/Paradata/Ref/Master questionnaire SI export rev0-NB.json"
settings["item_versions_file"] = "/Users/nejc/OneDrive - Univerza v Ljubljani/RR Projekti/2018
Paradata TP BL/Survey/Paradata/Ref/Common item names SI rev0-GČ-NB.csv"
settings["survey_id"] = 248758

# UAS corrections file.
# Specify the location of a file to correct wrongly identified device info from uas. It needs
to contain the following
# columns:
# - search_string : uas string or part of it to search for in paradata;
# - device_brand_corr: manufacturer name
# - device_model_corr: device model name or code
# - is_mobile_corr: bool whether mobile phone
# - is_tablet_corr: bool whether tablet
# - is_pc_corr: bool whether pc
# - match_type: type of match for info correction (full_uas | full_model_code |
partial_model_code | manual)
settings["uas_corrections_file"] = "/Users/nejc/OneDrive - Univerza v Ljubljani/RR
Projekti/2018 Paradata TP BL/Survey/Paradata/Ref/UAS corrections rev0-NB.csv"

# TODO: Ideas for additional paradata processing settings:
# - Use response and messages data to impute missing pageviews identifiers (currently always
performed);
# - additional option to replace page IDs using questionnaire metadata in case of conflict
(currently always performed).
# - Which sources to use when imputing pageviews identifiers (currently uses UAS and
response/messages data).
# - Specify whether only one UAS per respondent should be enforced. This is useful when we
know that the respondent
# - could not terminate the participation and return later to finish it using another
device/browser.

```

```

# - Use UAS correction file (currently always used and assumed it exists)
# - Merge pageview entries into one if no other events were logged during the pageview
(currently yes)

# %% SURVEY METADATA
# Parse questionnaire metadata. Note that the script is only checked for question types and
formats used in this
# survey. Other surveys may contain unsupported types.
survey_metadata = metadata_parse(settings["metadata_file"])

# Because response_option_id is not always unique (e.g. for grid questions it equals value),
we replace it by
# putting together question_id and response_option_id.
survey_metadata["response_options"]["response_option_unique_id"] =
survey_metadata["response_options"][
"question_id"].astype(str) + \

survey_metadata["response_options"][
"response_option_id"].astype(str)

# Create sequential page identifier.
# TODO: Zaradi konsistentnosti to shrani kot ref_ objekt in ne v survey_metadata.
survey_metadata["pages"]["page_seq"] = survey_metadata["pages"].index
survey_metadata["pages"]["page_seq"] = np.where(survey_metadata["pages"]["type"] == "intro",
0, survey_metadata["pages"]["page_seq"])
survey_metadata["pages"]["page_seq"] = np.where(survey_metadata["pages"]["type"] == "end",
999999, survey_metadata["pages"]["page_seq"])

# %% PAGEVIEWS
# Import data and rename columns.
pageviews_raw = pd.read_csv(
    settings["data_folder"] + "advanced_paradata_pageviews_" + str(settings["survey_id"]) +
".csv",
    quotechar="'")
pageviews_raw.rename(columns={"id": "pageview_id",
"ank_id": "survey_id",
"gru_id": "page_id",
"usr_id": "respondent_id",
"load_time": "load_ts",
"post_time": "post_ts",
"user_agent": "uas",
"language": "survey_lang",
"devicePixelRatio": "pixel_ratio",
"width": "screen_width",
"height": "screen_height",
"availWidth": "screen_width_avail",
"availHeight": "screen_height_avail",
"jquery_windowW": "viewport_width",
"jquery_windowH": "viewport_height",
"jquery_documentW": "page_width",
"jquery_documentH": "page_height"},
inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Convert timestamps into datetime format.
pageviews_raw["load_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(pageviews_raw["load_ts"],
format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
pageviews_raw["post_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(pageviews_raw["post_ts"],
format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")

# Check and log potential non-existing timestamps.
# IMPORTANT: Post timestamps were not used in this study and are therefore not addressed in
the code.
if pageviews_raw["load_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(
        ["pageviews_raw", "potential data loss", "Some pageview entries do not have valid
load_ts value.",
pageviews_raw[pageviews_raw["load_ts"].isna()]])

# Check for known invalid page_id values and set them to missing.
if ((pageviews_raw["page_id"] == 0) | (pageviews_raw["respondent_id"] == 0)).any():
    processing_log.append(["pageviews_raw", "missing/invalid data",
"Some pageview entries do not have a valid page ID. These IDs were
set to missing.",

```

```

        pageviews_raw[(pageviews_raw["page_id"] == 0) |
(pageviews_raw["respondent_id"] == 0)])

    pageviews_raw.replace({"page_id": {0: np.nan}, "respondent_id": {0: np.nan}, "recnum": {0:
np.nan}},
                           inplace=True)

# Check for other known invalid values and set them to missing.
# TODO: This would be good to log, too.
pageviews_raw.replace({"pixel_ratio": {0: np.nan},
                       "screen_width": {0: np.nan},
                       "screen_height": {0: np.nan},
                       "screen_width_avail": {0: np.nan},
                       "screen_height_avail": {0: np.nan},
                       "viewport_width": {0: np.nan},
                       "viewport_height": {0: np.nan},
                       "page_width": {0: np.nan},
                       "page_height": {0: np.nan}}, inplace=True)

# %% RESPONSES

# Import data and rename columns.
responses_raw = pd.read_csv(
    settings["data_folder"] + "advanced_paradata_responses_" + str(settings["survey_id"]) +
".csv",
    quotechar="'")
responses_raw.rename(columns={"id": "response_id",
                              "page_id": "pageview_id",
                              "spr_id": "spr_id_tmp",
                              "vre_id": "vre_id_tmp",
                              "time": "response_ts",
                              "event": "event_tmp",
                              "value": "value_tmp"},
                    inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Check for entries with known invalid identifier(s). They need to be removed to prevent
errors when merging
# with metadata.
if (responses_raw["spr_id_tmp"] == 0).any():
    processing_log.append(["responses_raw", "data deletion",
                          "Some entries do not have valid response ID and were removed to
prevent errors in further "
                          "processing.",
                          responses_raw[responses_raw["spr_id_tmp"] == 0]])
    responses_raw = responses_raw[responses_raw["spr_id_tmp"] != 0]

# Create a unique identifier for response options to match with metadata.
responses_raw["spr_vre_id_tmp"] = responses_raw["spr_id_tmp"].astype(str) +
responses_raw["vre_id_tmp"].astype(str)

# %% Derivation of question info from the survey metadata
# Process each question type in a separate dataframe. Basic identifiers and key info (e.g.
name and value) are
# obtained at this stage as well.
# IMPORTANT: This is not a general solution and may not work for question types that were not
used in this
# questionnaire.

# Get question names and types by merging the questions metadata..
responses_raw = pd.merge(responses_raw, survey_metadata["questions"][["question_id", "name",
"input"]],
                        left_on="spr_id_tmp", right_on="question_id", how="left")
responses_raw.rename(columns={"name": "question_name",
                              "type": "question_type",
                              "input": "question_input_type"}, inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Single answer radio:
# - get question_id from spr_id_tmp
# - because this is a single-item question, item_id equals question_id
# - get response_option_id from vre_id_tmp
responses_raw_single_answer = responses_raw[responses_raw["question_type"] ==
"single_answer"].copy()
responses_raw_single_answer["item_id"] = responses_raw_single_answer["question_id"]
responses_raw_single_answer["item_name"] = responses_raw_single_answer["question_name"]
responses_raw_single_answer = pd.merge(responses_raw_single_answer,

```

```

survey_metadata["response_options"][["response_option_id",
"response_option_unique_id",
                                "value"]],
                                left_on="vre_id_tmp", right_on="response_option_id",
how="left",
                                indicator="response_option_merge_status")
responses_raw_single_answer.rename(columns={"value": "response_option_code"}, inplace=True)

# Multiple answer checkbox
# - get question_id from spr_id_tmp
# - get item_id from vre_id_tmp for normal items
# - get response_option_id from vre_id_tmp for nonsubstantive response options
# - in case of nonsubstantive response options item_id and item_name equals question id and
name.
responses_raw_multi_answer = responses_raw[responses_raw["question_type"] ==
"multi_answer"].copy()
responses_raw_multi_answer = pd.merge(responses_raw_multi_answer,
survey_metadata["items"][["item_id", "name"]],
                                left_on="vre_id_tmp", right_on="item_id", how="left",
                                indicator="item_merge_status")
responses_raw_multi_answer = pd.merge(responses_raw_multi_answer,
survey_metadata["response_options"][["response_option_id",
"response_option_unique_id",
                                "value"]],
                                left_on="vre_id_tmp", right_on="response_option_id",
how="left",
                                indicator="response_option_merge_status")
responses_raw_multi_answer.rename(columns={"name": "item_name",
"value": "response_option_code"}, inplace=True,
errors="raise")
responses_raw_multi_answer["item_id"] = np.where(responses_raw_multi_answer["item_id"].isna(),
responses_raw_multi_answer["question_id"],
responses_raw_multi_answer["item_id"])
responses_raw_multi_answer["item_name"] =
np.where(responses_raw_multi_answer["item_name"].isna(),
responses_raw_multi_answer["question_name"],
responses_raw_multi_answer["item_name"])

# Open numeric
# - get question_id from spr_id_tmp
# - get answer_id from spr_vre_id_tmp (only for nonsubstantive if any; needs to use created
unique identifier
# due to repeated answer codes).
# - get item_id from items metadata by matching question_id. # IMPORTANT: This only works
because we have no
# multiple-item open-ended responses in this survey (i.e. we always have only one input
field in open
# questions).
responses_raw_open = responses_raw[responses_raw["question_type"] == "open"].copy()
responses_raw_open = pd.merge(responses_raw_open, survey_metadata["items"][["question_id",
"item_id", "name"]],
                                left_on="spr_id_tmp", right_on="question_id", how="left",
                                indicator="item_merge_status")
responses_raw_open = pd.merge(responses_raw_open,
survey_metadata["response_options"][["response_option_id",
"response_option_unique_id",
"value"]],
                                left_on="spr_vre_id_tmp", right_on="response_option_unique_id",
how="left",
                                indicator="response_option_merge_status")
responses_raw_open.rename(columns={"name": "item_name",
"value": "response_option_code"}, inplace=True,
errors="raise")
# Check if question_id from initial and merged database match. If yes, use only one. Otherwise
log an
# error and stop execution.
if (responses_raw_open["question_id_x"] != responses_raw_open["question_id_y"]).sum() == 0:
responses_raw_open.rename(columns={"question_id_x": "question_id"}, inplace=True)
responses_raw_open.drop("question_id_y", axis=1, inplace=True)

```

```

else:
    processing_log.append(["responses_raw", "data inconsistency",
                          "Conflicting questions IDs while merging item metadata for open
numeric questions.",
                          responses_raw_open[
                              (responses_raw_open["question_id_x"] !=
responses_raw_open["question_id_y"])]])
    raise ValueError('Conflicting questions IDs while merging item metadata for open numeric
questions.')
```

```

# Grid
# - get item_id from spr_id_tmp
# - get question_id from item_id and match missing question info
# - get answer_id from spr_vre_id_tmp (needs to use the created unique identifier )
# First we drop columns that are empty and will be filled by merging info from other data.
This removes the need
# to rename equally named columns from merged dataframes later.
responses_raw_grids = responses_raw[responses_raw["question_type"].isna()].copy()
responses_raw_grids.drop(["question_id", "question_name", "question_type",
"question_input_type"], axis=1,
                          inplace=True)
responses_raw_grids["item_id"] = responses_raw_grids["spr_id_tmp"]
responses_raw_grids = pd.merge(responses_raw_grids, survey_metadata["items"][["question_id",
"item_id", "name"]],
                              on="item_id", how="left", indicator="item_merge_status")
responses_raw_grids.rename(columns={"name": "question_name"}, inplace=True, errors="raise")
responses_raw_grids = pd.merge(responses_raw_grids,
                              survey_metadata["questions"][["question_id", "name", "type",
"input"]],
                              on="question_id", how="left",
indicator="question_merge_status")
responses_raw_grids.rename(columns={"name": "question_name",
"question_type": "question_type",
"input": "question_input_type"}, inplace=True,
errors="raise")
# Response_option_unique_id needs to be redefined, because spr_vre_id_tmp does not contain
question id with grid
# questions.
responses_raw_grids["response_option_unique_id"] =
responses_raw_grids["question_id"].astype(str) + \

responses_raw_grids["vre_id_tmp"].astype(str)
responses_raw_grids = pd.merge(responses_raw_grids,
survey_metadata["response_options"][["response_option_id",
"response_option_unique_id",
"value"]],
                              on="response_option_unique_id", how="left",
indicator="response_option_merge_status")
responses_raw_grids.rename(columns={"value": "response_option_code"}, inplace=True)

# Replace the original dataframe with edited data and tidy up.
responses_raw = responses_raw_single_answer.append(
    [responses_raw_multi_answer, responses_raw_open, responses_raw_grids])
responses_raw.drop(["item_merge_status", "question_merge_status",
"response_option_merge_status"], axis=1,
                    inplace=True)

# Create a new variable describing response action performed (instead of having two
variables).
responses_raw["response_action"] = "undefined"
responses_raw["response_action"] = np.where(
    (responses_raw["event_tmp"] == "radio_checkbox_change") & (responses_raw["value_tmp"] ==
"1"),
    "selected", responses_raw["response_action"])
responses_raw["response_action"] = np.where(
    (responses_raw["event_tmp"] == "radio_checkbox_change") & (responses_raw["value_tmp"] ==
"0"),
    "unselected", responses_raw["response_action"])
responses_raw["response_action"] = np.where(
    (responses_raw["event_tmp"] == "text_enter") | (responses_raw["event_tmp"] ==
"text_leave"),
    responses_raw["event_tmp"], responses_raw["response_action"])
responses_raw["response_value"] = np.where(

```

```

        (responses_raw["event_tmp"] == "text_enter") | (responses_raw["event_tmp"] ==
"text_leave"),
        responses_raw["value_tmp"], responses_raw["response_option_code"])
responses_raw["response_value"] = np.where(
    (responses_raw["response_action"] == "selected") & (responses_raw["question_type"] ==
"multi_answer") & (
        responses_raw["question_input_type"] == "checkbox"),
    "1", responses_raw["response_value"])
responses_raw["response_value"] = np.where(
    (responses_raw["response_action"] == "unselected") & (responses_raw["question_type"] ==
"multi_answer") & (
        responses_raw["question_input_type"] == "checkbox"),
    "0", responses_raw["response_value"])

# %% Finalisation
# Convert timestamps into datetime format and check for missing timestamps.
responses_raw["response_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(responses_raw["response_ts"],
                                              format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if responses_raw["response_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["responses_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some response entries do not have valid response_ts value.",
                          responses_raw[responses_raw["response_ts"].isna()]])

# Add page ids. This is done at this stage using metadata to enable potential imputation of
missing page ids
# during the processing of pageviews data.
responses_raw = pd.merge(responses_raw, survey_metadata["questions"][["question_id",
"page_id"]],
                        on="question_id", how="left", indicator="page_id_merge")
if (responses_raw["page_id_merge"] != "both").any():
    processing_log.append(["responses_raw", "unmerged entries",
                          "Some response entries were not assigned page_id value from the
questionnaire metadata.",
                          responses_raw[responses_raw["page_id_merge"] != "both"]])
responses_raw.rename(columns={"page_id": "page_id_meta"}, inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Keep only relevant variables, reordered column and change identifiers to int if none is
missing.
responses_raw = responses_raw[["response_id", "pageview_id", "response_ts", "question_id",
"question_name",
                                "question_type", "question_input_type", "item_id", "item_name",
                                "response_option_id", "response_option_unique_id",
"response_option_code",
                                "response_action", "response_value", "page_id_meta"]]
responses_raw["question_id"] = responses_raw["question_id"].astype(np.int64)

# Drop unneeded objects.
del responses_raw_grids
del responses_raw_multi_answer
del responses_raw_open
del responses_raw_single_answer

# %% MESSAGES

# Import data and rename columns.
messages_raw = pd.read_csv(settings["data_folder"] + "advanced_paradata_msg_" +
str(settings["survey_id"]) + ".csv",
                           quotechar="'")
messages_raw.rename(columns={"id": "msg_id",
                             "page_id": "pageview_id",
                             "time_display": "display_ts",
                             "time_close": "close_ts",
                             "type": "type",
                             "trigger_id": "trigger_question_id",
                             "trigger_type": "trigger_type",
                             "ignorable": "ignorable",
                             "text": "msg_text",
                             "action": "respondent_action"},
                    inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Merge with question info.
messages_raw = pd.merge(messages_raw, survey_metadata["questions"][["question_id", "name",
"type"]],
                        left_on="trigger_question_id", right_on="question_id", how="left",
                        indicator="questions_merge")
if (messages_raw["questions_merge"] != "both").any():

```

```

        processing_log.append(["messages_raw", "unmerged entries",
                              "Some response message entries were not assigned question info from
the questionnaire "
                              "metadata.",
                              messages_raw[messages_raw["questions_merge"] != "both"]])
messages_raw.drop(columns="question_id", inplace=True)

# Identify message type and check that no exceptions occurred. Multiple original variables are
used to assure
# that all data are consistently logged. Note that several conditions need to be used, because
the "ignorable"
# variable provided by lKA is not valid for all message types (e.g. numeric validations).
messages_raw["ignorable"] = np.where(messages_raw["ignorable"] == 1, True, False)
messages_raw["msg_type"] = "undefined"
messages_raw["msg_type"] = np.where(
    (messages_raw["trigger_type"] == "sof") | (messages_raw["trigger_type"] == "har"),
    "item_nonresponse",
    messages_raw["msg_type"])
messages_raw["msg_type"] = np.where(messages_raw["trigger_type"] == "num", "invalid_number",
                                   messages_raw["msg_type"])
if (messages_raw["msg_type"] == "undefined").any():
    processing_log.append(
        ["messages_raw", "missing/invalid data", "Some response messages are of unknown
type.",
        messages_raw[messages_raw["msg_type"] == "undefined"]])

# Convert timestamps to datetime format and check for missing timestamps.
messages_raw["display_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(messages_raw["display_ts"],
                                             format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if messages_raw["display_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["messages_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some response message entries do not have valid display_ts
value.",
                          messages_raw[messages_raw["display_ts"].isna()]])
messages_raw["close_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(messages_raw["close_ts"],
                                             format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if messages_raw["close_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["messages_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some response message entries do not have valid close_ts value.",
                          messages_raw[messages_raw["close_ts"].isna()]])

# Add page ids. This is done at this stage using metadata to enable potential imputation of
missing page ids
# during the processing of pageviews data.
messages_raw = pd.merge(messages_raw, survey_metadata["questions"][["question_id",
"page_id"]],
                        left_on="trigger_question_id", right_on="question_id", how="left",
                        indicator="page_id_merge")
if (messages_raw["page_id_merge"] != "both").any():
    processing_log.append(["messages_raw", "unmerged entries",
                          "Some response message entries were not assigned page_id value from
the questionnaire metadata.",
                          messages_raw[messages_raw["page_id_merge"] != "both"]])

# Rename and reorder columns and keep only relevant variables.
messages_raw.rename(columns={"name": "trigger_question_name",
                             "page_id": "page_id_meta"}, inplace=True, errors="raise")
messages_raw = messages_raw[["msg_id", "pageview_id", "msg_type", "display_ts", "close_ts",
"trigger_question_id",
                             "trigger_question_name", "ignorable", "msg_text",
"respondent_action",
                             "page_id_meta"]]

# %% POINTER MOVEMENT

# Import data and rename columns.
pointer_raw = pd.read_csv(settings["data_folder"] + "advanced_paradata_pointer_" +
str(settings["survey_id"]) + ".csv",
                           quotechar="")
pointer_raw.rename(columns={"id": "move_id",
                             "page_id": "pageview_id",
                             "time_start": "move_start_ts",
                             "time_end": "move_end_ts",
                             "pos_x_start": "start_coord_x",
                             "pos_y_start": "start_coord_y",

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        "pos_x_end": "end_coord_x",
        "pos_y_end": "end_coord_y",
        "distance": "move_distance"},
    inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Convert timestamps to datetime format and check for missing timestamps.
pointer_raw["move_start_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(pointer_raw["move_start_ts"],
                                             format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
pointer_raw["move_end_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(pointer_raw["move_end_ts"],
                                             format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if pointer_raw["move_start_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["pointer_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some pointer movement events do not have valid move_start_ts
value.",
                          pointer_raw[pointer_raw["move_start_ts"].isna()]])
if pointer_raw["move_end_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["pointer_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some pointer movement events do not have valid move_end_ts
value.",
                          pointer_raw[pointer_raw["move_end_ts"].isna()]])

# %% OTHER PARADATA
# This bit only imports the whole "other" dataset as a temporary object that is later used to
create several datasets
# containing different types of paradata.

# Import data and rename columns.
other_raw = pd.read_csv(
    settings["data_folder"] + "advanced_paradata_other_" + str(settings["survey_id"]) +
    ".csv",
    quotechar="'")

# %% PAGE SCROLLING

# Take relevant events from the dataset and rename columns.
page_scrolls_raw = other_raw.loc[other_raw["event"] == "scroll_page", ["id", "page_id",
"time", "pos_x", "pos_y"]].copy()
page_scrolls_raw.rename(columns={"id": "scroll_id",
                                "page_id": "pageview_id",
                                "time": "scroll_ts",
                                "pos_x": "scroll_coord_x",
                                "pos_y": "scroll_coord_y"},
                        inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Convert timestamps to datetime format and check for missing timestamps.
page_scrolls_raw["scroll_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(page_scrolls_raw["scroll_ts"],
                                             format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if page_scrolls_raw["scroll_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["page_scrolls_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some scroll events do not have valid scroll_ts value.",
                          page_scrolls_raw[page_scrolls_raw["scroll_ts"].isna()]])

# %% CLICK

# Take relevant events from the dataset and rename columns.
clicks_raw = other_raw.loc[
    other_raw["event"] == "click", ["id", "page_id", "time", "pos_x", "pos_y", "div_id",
"div_class", "div_type"]].copy()
clicks_raw.rename(columns={"id": "click_id",
                            "page_id": "pageview_id",
                            "time": "click_ts",
                            "pos_x": "coord_x",
                            "pos_y": "coord_y"},
                  inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Convert timestamps to datetime format and check for missing timestamps.
clicks_raw["click_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(clicks_raw["click_ts"],
                                       format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if clicks_raw["click_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["clicks_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some scroll events do not have valid click_ts value.",
                          clicks_raw[clicks_raw["click_ts"].isna()]])

# %% FOCUS CHANGES
# Take relevant events from the dataset and rename columns.
focus_changes_raw = other_raw.loc[

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        (other_raw["event"] == "focus") | (other_raw["event"] == "blur"),
        ["id", "page_id", "time", "event"]).copy()
focus_changes_raw.rename(columns={"id": "focus_change_id",
                                   "page_id": "pageview_id",
                                   "time": "focus_change_ts",
                                   "event": "change_type"},
                          inplace=True, errors="raise")

# Convert timestamps to datetime format and check for missing timestamps.
focus_changes_raw["focus_change_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(focus_changes_raw["focus_change_ts"],
                                                       format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if focus_changes_raw["focus_change_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["focus_changes_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some scroll events do not have valid focus_change_ts value.",
                          focus_changes_raw[focus_changes_raw["focus_change_ts"].isna()]])

# %% VIEW CHANGES
# Take relevant events from the dataset and rename columns.
view_changes_raw = other_raw.loc[
    (other_raw["event"] == "resize") | (other_raw["event"] == "pinch_resize") |
    (other_raw["event"] == "orientation_change"),
    ["id", "page_id", "time", "event", "value", "pos_x", "pos_y"]].copy()
# TODO Check the names of resolution variables and rename them if needed.
view_changes_raw.rename(columns={"id": "view_change_id",
                                   "page_id": "pageview_id",
                                   "time": "view_change_ts",
                                   "event": "change_type",
                                   "value": "value_field_1",
                                   "pos_x": "res_h",
                                   "pos_y": "res_v"},
                          inplace=True, errors="raise")

# In raw data we only change the name of events to make it clearer for further processing.
view_changes_raw["change_type"] = np.where(view_changes_raw["change_type"] == "resize",
                                           "zoom_or_window_resize",
                                           view_changes_raw["change_type"])
view_changes_raw["change_type"] = np.where(view_changes_raw["change_type"] == "pinch_resize",
                                           "pinch_zoom",
                                           view_changes_raw["change_type"])

# Convert timestamps to datetime format and check for missing timestamps.
view_changes_raw["view_change_ts"] = pd.to_datetime(view_changes_raw["view_change_ts"],
                                                    format="%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S.%f", errors="coerce")
if view_changes_raw["view_change_ts"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["view_changes_raw", "potential data loss",
                          "Some scroll events do not have valid view_change_ts value.",
                          view_changes_raw[view_changes_raw["view_change_ts"].isna()]])

# %% ALL EVENTS LOG
# The all events log contains timestamps and types of logged events. This is used for
# diagnostics and identification
# of inactivity times.
# Events that have multiple timestamps logged as part of the same record (e.g. start and end
# time in one row) are
# split into several events. Note that IDs of such events are repeated (i.e. not all event_id
# values are unique).
# Note page post should be added, but was not recorded in this survey.
# TODO: Include events from other.

event_list_raw = pd.concat([pageviews_raw[["pageview_id", "load_ts"]],
                            responses_raw[["response_id", "pageview_id", "response_ts"]],
                            messages_raw[["msg_id", "pageview_id", "display_ts"]],
                            messages_raw[["msg_id", "pageview_id", "close_ts"]],
                            pointer_raw[["move_id", "pageview_id", "move_start_ts"]],
                            pointer_raw[["move_id", "pageview_id", "move_end_ts"]],
                            page_scrolls_raw[["scroll_id", "pageview_id", "scroll_ts"]],
                            clicks_raw[["click_id", "pageview_id", "click_ts"]],
                            focus_changes_raw[["focus_change_id", "pageview_id",
                                                "focus_change_ts", "change_type"]],
                            view_changes_raw[["view_change_id", "pageview_id",
                                                "view_change_ts", "change_type"]]])

# Create unified event ID, event type and event timestamp variables. The code below takes
# advantage of having uniquely

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# named timestamp variables in each dataframe.
event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["load_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["pageview_id"], np.nan)
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["load_ts"].notna(), "pageview", np.nan)
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["load_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["load_ts"], pd.NaT)

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["response_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["response_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["response_ts"].notna(), "response",
event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["response_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["response_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["display_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["msg_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["display_ts"].notna(),
"message_display", event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["display_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["display_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["close_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["msg_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["close_ts"].notna(), "message_close",
event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["close_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["close_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["move_start_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["move_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["move_start_ts"].notna(),
"pointer_move_start", event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["move_start_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["move_start_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["move_end_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["move_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["move_end_ts"].notna(),
"pointer_move_end", event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["move_end_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["move_end_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["scroll_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["scroll_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["scroll_ts"].notna(), "scroll",
event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["scroll_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["scroll_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["click_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["click_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["click_ts"].notna(), "click",
event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["click_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["click_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["focus_change_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["focus_change_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where((event_list_raw["focus_change_ts"].notna()) &
(event_list_raw["change_type"] == "focus"),
"window_focus", event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where((event_list_raw["focus_change_ts"].notna()) &
(event_list_raw["change_type"] == "blur"),
"window_blur", event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["focus_change_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["focus_change_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_id"] = np.where(event_list_raw["view_change_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["view_change_id"], event_list_raw["event_id"])
event_list_raw["event_type"] = np.where(event_list_raw["view_change_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["change_type"], event_list_raw["event_type"])
event_list_raw["event_ts"] = np.where(event_list_raw["view_change_ts"].notna(),
event_list_raw["view_change_ts"], event_list_raw["event_ts"])

event_list_raw["event_ts"] = event_list_raw["event_ts"].astype(np.datetime64)

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2.3 Paradata processing

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# PARADATA PROCESSING
# This code takes imported paradata and performs various data processing operations to clean,
remove duplicates and
# invalid data, handle missings etc. Its outputs are used as input for paradata analysis.

# It is probably good idea to define function to process each paradata type. This is not done
in this script but should
# be quite easy to do. In this case, processing settings should be defined at the level of
individual functions.
# This file needs to be run second, after metadata parser. Code contained in other files
assume existence of some objects
# created by this code.

import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import user_agents as ua

# This check is therefore
# only perform for non-missing data in page_id and page_id_meta. Depending on the settings,
conflicting
# page_id_meta values are either set to missing or used to replace the existing page_id values

# %% PAGEVIEWS
pageviews_proc = pageviews_raw.copy()

# %% Imputation of missing identifier data
# TODO: Check that the required tables of raw response and messages data exist. Messages data
are useful for
# cases where no response was provided, triggering item nonresponse reminder. This is only
applicable for pages
# containing at least one question with nonresponse reminder (or any other kind of validation)
and pageviews
# during which such validation was triggered.

# STAGE 1: Impute page ids based on responses and messages data.
# Create a list for matching pageviews and page ids from raw responses and messages data.
pageview_page_ids = responses_raw[["pageview_id", "page_id_meta"]].drop_duplicates()
pageview_page_ids = pageview_page_ids.append(messages_raw[["pageview_id",
"page_id_meta"]].drop_duplicates())
pageview_page_ids.drop_duplicates(inplace=True)

# Check that all pageview ids are unique
if pageview_page_ids["pageview_id"].is_unique == False:
    processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "inconsistent value",
                          "Not all pageviews IDs used for imputation of missing identifiers
are unique. "
                          "This may cause errors in the script performance and indicate
underlying problems.",
                          ])

pageview_page_ids[pageview_page_ids["pageview_id"].duplicated(keep=False) == True]]

# Merge page_id_meta with pageview entries and check for consistency against the existing page
ids. This is done
# to verify the consistency of data used for imputation. Note that missings may occur in
page_id_meta in various
# scenarios, e.g. when the respondent goes back and does not change any response as this will
trigger no
# response entries or INR reminder entries which are used to derive page_id_meta values.
pageviews_proc = pd.merge(pageviews_proc, pageview_page_ids, how="left", on="pageview_id",
indicator="page_id_merge")
if ((pageviews_proc["page_id"].notnull() & (pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"].notnull() &
(pageviews_proc["page_id"] != pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"])).any():
    processing_log.append(
        ["pageviews_proc", "inconsistent identifiers",
         "For some pageviews entries there is a mismatch between existing page_ids and
page_id_meta values used for "
         "imputation. This may be caused by changes in survey page breaks during the data "
         "collection. The original page_ids for these cases will be replaced by page_id_meta "
         "values, existing values are logged.",
         pageviews_proc[pageviews_proc["page_id"].notnull() &
         (pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"].notnull() &
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        (pageviews_proc["page_id"] != pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"]]))
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where(((pageviews_proc["page_id"].notnull()) &
        (pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"].notnull()) &
        (pageviews_proc["page_id"] !=
pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"])),
        pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"],
pageviews_proc["page_id"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"].fillna(pageviews_proc["page_id_meta"], inplace=True)

del pageview_page_ids

# "Manually" correct page IDs of pages containing only captions that were not identified
above. This is due to changes in page breaks
# that were done during the data collection. However, some changes may still be missed :-/
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511226),
        12511228, pageviews_proc["page_id"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511205),
        12511206, pageviews_proc["page_id"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511248),
        12511253, pageviews_proc["page_id"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511256),
        12511261, pageviews_proc["page_id"])

processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "manual correction of identifiers",
        """"Some page identifiers were manually corrected. The complete source
code is provided here:
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511226),
        12511228, pageviews_proc["page_id"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511205),
        12511206, pageviews_proc["page_id"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511248),
        12511253, pageviews_proc["page_id"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["recnum"] >= 50) &
        (pageviews_proc["recnum"] <= 101) & (pageviews_proc["page_id"] == 12511256),
        12511261, pageviews_proc["page_id"])"""])

# STAGE 2: Impute respondent IDs and the remaining missing page IDs.
# Create a list of entries with missing ID.
imputed_ids = pageviews_proc.loc[
pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].isnull(), ["pageview_id", "respondent_id", "load_ts", "uas"]]
imputed_ids.sort_values("load_ts", inplace=True)

# Identify potential imputation sources as entries with nonmissing identifiers that have the
matching UAS and
# were present in the survey during the hour when any missings with such UA occurred. First
the matching
# candidate respondents are identified, then pageviews entries of these respondents are
selected to find the nearest
# pageview entry candidate to be used for imputation.
resp_id_sources = pageviews_proc.loc[
pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].notna(), ["respondent_id", "load_ts", "uas"]].copy()
resp_id_sources["hr_uas"] = resp_id_sources["load_ts"].dt.strftime("%Y%m%d%H") + "_" + \
        resp_id_sources["uas"]
resp_id_sources = resp_id_sources.groupby(["respondent_id", "uas"])["load_ts"].agg(
["min", "max"]).reset_index()

def impute_pageview_ids(i_row):
    i_date = i_row["load_ts"]
    i_uas = i_row["uas"]
    # Check the list of potential imputation sources for match on both: UAS and the period
between the first and
    # the last page load event covering the time when the page load event with missing ID
occurred.
    i_candidate_respondents = resp_id_sources[
        (resp_id_sources["uas"] == i_uas) & (resp_id_sources["min"] < i_date) & (
            resp_id_sources["max"] > i_date)]
    i_n_unique = i_candidate_respondents["respondent_id"].nunique()

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    if i_n_unique == 1:
        # If only one respondent ID matches the UAS and the period during which the event with
        # missing ID occurred,
        # the nearest previous pageview by this respondent is used to provide the data for the
        # missing entry.
        i_candidate_pageviews = pageviews_proc[

pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].isin(i_candidate_respondents["respondent_id"])] .copy()
        i_candidate_pageviews = i_candidate_pageviews[
            (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]).dt.total_seconds() > 0]
        i_delta_min = (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]).min()
        i_row["imp_respondent_id"] = i_candidate_pageviews.loc[
            (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]) == i_delta_min,
"respondent_id"].iloc[0]
        i_row["match"] = "single_match"
        i_row["no_matches"] = i_n_unique
        i_row["match_load_time_diff"] = i_delta_min.total_seconds()
        i_row["source_pageview_id"] = i_candidate_pageviews.loc[
            (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]) == i_delta_min, "pageview_id"].iloc[0]
        i_row["imp_recnum"] = \
            pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == i_row["source_pageview_id"],
"recnum"].iloc[0]
        i_row["imp_page_id"] = \
            pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == i_row["source_pageview_id"],
"page_id"].iloc[0]
        elif i_n_unique > 1:
            # If pageload events with several different respondent ID entries match the UAS and
            # the period during which
            # the event with missing ID occurred, the entry with the nearest previous timestamp
            # among these is used to
            # provide the data for the missing entry.
            i_candidate_pageviews = pageviews_proc[

pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].isin(i_candidate_respondents["respondent_id"])] .copy()
            i_candidate_pageviews = i_candidate_pageviews[
                (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]).dt.total_seconds() > 0]
            i_delta_min = (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]).min()
            i_row["imp_respondent_id"] = i_candidate_pageviews.loc[
                (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]) == i_delta_min,
"respondent_id"].iloc[0]
            i_row["match"] = "nearest_TS_UAS"
            i_row["no_matches"] = i_n_unique
            i_row["match_load_time_diff"] = i_delta_min.total_seconds()
            i_row["source_pageview_id"] = i_candidate_pageviews.loc[
                (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]) == i_delta_min, "pageview_id"].iloc[0]
            i_row["imp_recnum"] = \
                pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == i_row["source_pageview_id"],
"recnum"].iloc[0]
            i_row["imp_page_id"] = \
                pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == i_row["source_pageview_id"],
"page_id"].iloc[0]
            else:
                # If no matches by UAS and the first-last timestamp period are found, the respondent
                # ID from the entry with
                # a matching UAS and the nearest previous timestamp is used.
                i_candidate_pageviews = pageviews_proc[
                    (pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].notna()) & (pageviews_proc["uas"] ==
i_uas)].copy()
                i_candidate_pageviews = i_candidate_pageviews[
                    (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]).dt.total_seconds() > 0]
                i_delta_min = (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]).min()
                if i_candidate_pageviews.empty == False:
                    i_delta_min = abs((i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"] - i_date)).min()
                    i_row["imp_respondent_id"] = i_candidate_pageviews.loc[
                        (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]) == i_delta_min,
"respondent_id"].iloc[0]
                    i_row["match"] = "nearest_UAS"
                    i_row["no_matches"] = i_n_unique
                    i_row["match_load_time_diff"] = i_delta_min.total_seconds()
                    i_row["source_pageview_id"] = i_candidate_pageviews.loc[
                        (i_date - i_candidate_pageviews["load_ts"]) == i_delta_min,
"pageview_id"].iloc[0]
                    i_row["imp_recnum"] = \
                        pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] ==
i_row["source_pageview_id"], "recnum"].iloc[0]
                    i_row["imp_page_id"] = \

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        pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] ==
i_row["source_pageview_id"], "page_id"].iloc[0]
    else:
        i_row["imp_respondent_id"] = np.nan
        i_row["match"] = "no match"
        i_row["no_matches"] = np.nan
        i_row["match_load_time_diff"] = np.nan
        i_row["source_pageview_id"] = np.nan
        i_row["imp_recnum"] = np.nan
        i_row["imp_page_id"] = np.nan
    return i_row

# Impute missing IDs.
imputed_ids = imputed_ids.apply(impute_pageview_ids, axis=1)
pageviews_proc = pd.merge(pageviews_proc,
                           imputed_ids[["pageview_id", "imp_respondent_id", "imp_recnum",
"imp_page_id",
                                       "match", "match_load_time_diff",
"source_pageview_id"]],
                           on="pageview_id", how="left")
pageviews_proc["respondent_id"] = np.where(pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].isna(),
                                           pageviews_proc["imp_respondent_id"],
                                           pageviews_proc["respondent_id"])
pageviews_proc["recnum"] = np.where(pageviews_proc["recnum"].isna(),
                                     pageviews_proc["imp_recnum"],
                                     pageviews_proc["recnum"])
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = np.where(pageviews_proc["page_id"].isna(),
                                       pageviews_proc["imp_page_id"],
                                       pageviews_proc["page_id"])

# Save the imputation info in the processing log.
processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "missing values imputation",
                    "Imputation of missing respondent and page identifiers in pageviews data
has been performed. "
                    "This log entry contains the list of potential replacements; actual
replacements have been "
                    "performed only where data was missing.", imputed_ids])

del imputed_ids
del resp_id_sources

# Handle the remaining entries with missing page/respondent IDs.
# Check whether any other paradata events occurred during these pageviews; for those we tried
to manually find the IDs. If ID could not
# be matched manually they were dropped along other remaining entries with missing IDs.
missing_ids = pageviews_proc[(pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].isna() |
pageviews_proc["page_id"].isna()).copy()]
missing_ids["has_events"] =
missing_ids["pageview_id"].isin(event_list_raw.loc[event_list_raw["event_type"] != "pageview",
"pageview_id"])

pageviews_proc["respondent_id"] = np.where(pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == 12376, 30754752,
pageviews_proc["respondent_id"])
pageviews_proc["recnum"] = np.where(pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == 12376, 154,
pageviews_proc["recnum"])
missing_ids = missing_ids[missing_ids["pageview_id"] != 12376]

pageviews_proc = pageviews_proc[(pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].notna() &
pageviews_proc["page_id"].notna())]

processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "missing values imputation / data deletion",
                    """"Respondent or page identifiers for some pageview entries were
manually corrected using the code below.
Others were deleted and are logged. Check the has_events column to see if any other paradata
events were associated with deleted pageviews.
Code:
pageviews_proc["respondent_id"] = np.where(pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == 12376, 30754752,
pageviews_proc["respondent_id"])
pageviews_proc["recnum"] = np.where(pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] == 12376, 154,
pageviews_proc["recnum"])""",
                    missing_ids])
del missing_ids

# Remove temporary variables used for imputation.
pageviews_proc.drop(columns=["page_id_meta", "page_id_merge", "imp_respondent_id",
"imp_recnum", "imp_page_id", "match", "match_load_time_diff",

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        "source_pageview_id"], inplace=True)

# %% Device information from UAS

# Check for missing UAS.
if pageviews_proc["uas"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "missing values", "Some pageview entries have
missing UAS",
        pageviews_proc[pageviews_proc["uas"].isna()]])

# Parse UAS to get device info.
pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"] = pageviews_proc["uas"].apply(lambda uas: ua.parse(uas))
pageviews_proc["browser_family"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.browser.family)
pageviews_proc["browser_version"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.browser.version_string)
pageviews_proc["os_family"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.os.family)
pageviews_proc["os_version"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.os.version_string)
pageviews_proc["device_brand"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.device.brand)
pageviews_proc["device_model"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.device.model)
pageviews_proc["is_mobile"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.is_mobile)
pageviews_proc["is_tablet"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.is_tablet)
pageviews_proc["is_pc"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas: i_uas.is_pc)
pageviews_proc["touch_capable"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas:
i_uas.is_touch_capable)
pageviews_proc["bot"] = pageviews_proc["parsed_uas"].apply(lambda i_uas: i_uas.is_bot)
pageviews_proc.drop("parsed_uas", axis=1, inplace=True)

# Correct known cases of incorrect or duplicate device type. E.g. with some tablets, the UAS
parser identifies more
# than one device type from the UAS. External file - if exists - is used to perform
corrections.
ref_data["uas_corrections"] = pd.read_csv(settings["uas_corrections_file"], quotechar='')
uas_corrections = ref_data["uas_corrections"]

# Merge by full uas, full model name and partial model name. For the latter two options, we
first need to
# check whether full or partial model name is contained in the entry string and store it to be
used as
# merging variable. Corrections are preserved in this order, i.e. full uas match has the
highest priority while
# partial model match has the lowest priority.
full_model = uas_corrections[uas_corrections["match_type"] ==
"full_model_code"]["search_string"]
partial_model = uas_corrections[uas_corrections["match_type"] ==
"partial_model_code"]["search_string"]
pageviews_proc["full_model_match"] = pageviews_proc["uas"].str.extract("(" +
"|".join(full_model) + ")",
                                                    expand=False)
pageviews_proc["partial_model_match"] = pageviews_proc["uas"].str.extract(
    "(" + "|".join(partial_model) + ")",
    expand=False)

pageviews_proc = pd.merge(pageviews_proc, uas_corrections, how="left", left_on="uas",
right_on="search_string",
                           indicator="uas_merge")
pageviews_proc = pd.merge(pageviews_proc, uas_corrections, how="left",
left_on="full_model_match",
                           right_on="search_string", suffixes=("", "_1"),
                           indicator="full_model_merge")
pageviews_proc = pd.merge(pageviews_proc, uas_corrections, how="left",
left_on="partial_model_match",
                           right_on="search_string", suffixes=("", "_2"),
                           indicator="partial_model_merge")

pageviews_proc[["device_brand_old", "device_model_old", "is_mobile_old", "is_tablet_old",
"is_pc_old"]] = pageviews_proc[["device_brand", "device_model", "is_mobile",
"is_tablet", "is_pc"]]

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# TODO: Putting _corr variables together first may not be necessary and could be directly used
to replace original
# values.
pageviews_proc["device_brand_corr"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] == "both"),
    pageviews_proc["device_brand_corr_1"],
    np.where((pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] !=
"both") & (
        pageviews_proc["partial_model_merge"] == "both"),
        pageviews_proc["device_brand_corr_2"],
        pageviews_proc["device_brand_corr"]))
pageviews_proc["device_model_corr"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] == "both"),
    pageviews_proc["device_model_corr_1"],
    np.where((pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] !=
"both") & (
        pageviews_proc["partial_model_merge"] == "both"),
        pageviews_proc["device_model_corr_2"],
        pageviews_proc["device_model_corr"]))
pageviews_proc["is_mobile_corr"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] == "both"),
    pageviews_proc["is_mobile_corr_1"],
    np.where((pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] !=
"both") & (
        pageviews_proc["partial_model_merge"] == "both"),
        pageviews_proc["is_mobile_corr_2"],
        pageviews_proc["is_mobile_corr"]))
pageviews_proc["is_tablet_corr"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] == "both"),
    pageviews_proc["is_tablet_corr_1"],
    np.where((pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] !=
"both") & (
        pageviews_proc["partial_model_merge"] == "both"),
        pageviews_proc["is_tablet_corr_2"],
        pageviews_proc["is_tablet_corr"]))
pageviews_proc["is_pc_corr"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] == "both"),
    pageviews_proc["is_pc_corr_1"],
    np.where((pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] !=
"both") & (
        pageviews_proc["partial_model_merge"] == "both"),
        pageviews_proc["is_pc_corr_2"],
        pageviews_proc["is_pc_corr"]))
pageviews_proc["match_type"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] == "both"),
    pageviews_proc["match_type_1"],
    np.where((pageviews_proc["uas_merge"] != "both") & (pageviews_proc["full_model_merge"] !=
"both") & (
        pageviews_proc["partial_model_merge"] == "both"),
        pageviews_proc["match_type_2"],
        pageviews_proc["match_type"]))

pageviews_proc.drop(columns=["device_brand_corr_1", "device_brand_corr_2",
"device_model_corr_1",
                                "device_model_corr_2", "is_mobile_corr_1", "is_mobile_corr_2",
"is_tablet_corr_1",
                                "is_tablet_corr_2", "is_pc_corr_1", "is_pc_corr_2",
"match_type_1", "match_type_2",
                                "search_string", "search_string_1", "search_string_2",
"full_model_match",
                                "partial_model_match", "uas_merge", "full_model_merge",
"partial_model_merge"],
                    inplace=True)

pageviews_proc["device_brand"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["device_brand_corr"].notna()) & (pageviews_proc["match_type"].notna()),
    pageviews_proc["device_brand_corr"],
    pageviews_proc["device_brand"])
pageviews_proc["device_model"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["device_model_corr"].notna()) & (pageviews_proc["match_type"].notna()),
    pageviews_proc["device_model_corr"],
    pageviews_proc["device_model"])
pageviews_proc["is_mobile"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["is_mobile_corr"].notna()) & (pageviews_proc["match_type"].notna()),
    pageviews_proc["is_mobile_corr"],
    pageviews_proc["is_mobile"])

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pageviews_proc["is_tablet"] = np.where(
    (pageviews_proc["is_tablet_corr"].notna()) & (pageviews_proc["match_type"].notna()),
    pageviews_proc["is_tablet_corr"],
    pageviews_proc["is_tablet"])
pageviews_proc["is_pc"] = np.where((pageviews_proc["is_pc_corr"].notna()) &
    (pageviews_proc["match_type"].notna()),
    pageviews_proc["is_pc_corr"],
    pageviews_proc["is_pc"])

# Log changes.
processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "data modification",
    "Changes have been applied to some device variables based on the UAS
    corrections file. "
    "Note that the log may also contain some cases for which variables were
    not modified. "
    "This is most likely due to patial model match not bringing additional
    information "
    "to currently available",
    pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["match_type"].notna(),
        ["pageview_id", "recnum", "device_brand",
        "device_brand_old",
        "device_model", "device_model_old", "is_mobile",
        "is_mobile_old",
        "is_tablet", "is_tablet_old", "is_pc", "is_pc_old",
        "match_type"]]])

# Drop correction variables as they are not longer needed.
pageviews_proc.drop(columns=["device_brand_corr", "device_model_corr", "is_tablet_corr",
    "is_mobile_corr", "is_pc_corr", "match_type", "device_brand_old",
    "device_model_old", "is_mobile_old", "is_tablet_old",
    "is_pc_old"], inplace=True)

# Set nonsubstantive values to missing and change None to NaN for consistency.
pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["browser_family"] == "", "browser_family"] = np.nan
pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["browser_version"] == "", "browser_version"] = np.nan
pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["os_family"] == "", "os_family"] = np.nan
pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["os_version"] == "", "os_version"] = np.nan
pageviews_proc.loc[(pageviews_proc["device_brand"] == "") | (
    pageviews_proc["device_brand"] == "Generic") | (pageviews_proc["device_brand"] ==
    "Generic_Android"),
    "device_brand"] = np.nan
pageviews_proc.loc[(pageviews_proc["device_model"] == "") | (pageviews_proc["device_model"] ==
    "Smartphone"),
    "device_model"] = np.nan

pageviews_proc["browser_family"].fillna(value=np.nan, inplace=True)
pageviews_proc["browser_version"].fillna(value=np.nan, inplace=True)
pageviews_proc["os_family"].fillna(value=np.nan, inplace=True)
pageviews_proc["os_version"].fillna(value=np.nan, inplace=True)
pageviews_proc["device_brand"].fillna(value=np.nan, inplace=True)
pageviews_proc["device_model"].fillna(value=np.nan, inplace=True)

# Change relevant variables to categorical.
pageviews_proc["browser_family"] = pageviews_proc["browser_family"].astype("category")
pageviews_proc["os_family"] = pageviews_proc["os_family"].astype("category")
pageviews_proc["device_brand"] = pageviews_proc["device_brand"].astype("category")

# Create a unified device type variable and check for potential entries with two or more
devices identified.
pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["is_pc"] == True, "device_type"] = "computer"
pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["is_mobile"] == True, "device_type"] = "mobile_phone"
pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc["is_tablet"] == True, "device_type"] = "tablet"
pageviews_proc["device_type"] = pageviews_proc["device_type"].astype("category")

# Check for missing values in the device variable.
if pageviews_proc["device_type"].isna().any():
    processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "missing/invalid data",
        "Device type could not be determined from the UAS data for some
        entries.",
        pageviews_proc[pageviews_proc["device_type"].isna()]])

# Check for cases with more than one type of device assigned and set them to missing.
if (pageviews_proc[["is_mobile", "is_tablet", "is_pc"]].sum(axis=1) > 1).any():
    pageviews_proc.loc[pageviews_proc[["is_mobile", "is_tablet", "is_pc"]].sum(axis=1) > 1,
    "device_type"] = np.nan
    processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "missing/invalid data",

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        "The UAS parser assigned more than one device type to some pageview
entries. These values were set as missing/invalid.",
        pageviews_proc[pageviews_proc[["is_mobile", "is_tablet",
"is_pc"]].sum(axis=1) > 1]])

# TODO: Preverjanje, če naprava ni konstantna znotraj vsakega respondent_id, pod pogojem, da
je to zahtevano v nastavitvi.
# Treba je upoštevati, da se UAS lahko spremeni zaradi vmesne nadgradnje brskalnika, tako da
morda je za začetek
# OK gledeati, če je tip brskalnika in tip naprave enak. Pri tem kot dodatnih pogoji
sprogramiramo.

# Drop dummy device variables.
pageviews_proc.drop(columns=["is_pc", "is_tablet", "is_mobile"], inplace=True)

del full_model
del partial_model

# %% Final editing and tidying up

# Some pageviews entries occur due to technical reasons that are not completely understood
yet. Sequential pageview entries for the same
# page that have no other recorded paradata events are therefore removed. Because we only
observe pageloads, we do not have to alter
# the timestamp for the kept events under assumption that "ghost" events always occur after
the "valid" event and not before it. The
# check is performed that such pageview is immediately preceded by a valid pageview event on
the same page.
# TODO: Ghost events should be further researched to confirm that they only occur sequentially
after the real event and never before it.
pageviews_proc["new_page"] =
pageviews_proc.sort_values(['respondent_id', 'load_ts']).groupby('respondent_id')['page_id'].diff().astype(bool)
pageviews_proc["has_events"] =
pageviews_proc["pageview_id"].isin(event_list_raw.loc[event_list_raw["event_type"] !=
"pageview", "pageview_id"])

# Pageview duration is calculated for control.
pageviews_proc["pageview_duration"] = pageviews_proc.sort_values(
    ['respondent_id', 'load_ts']).groupby('respondent_id')['load_ts'].diff(-1).dt.total_seconds()*(-1)

processing_log.append(["pageviews_proc", "data deletion", "Pageview entries without other
paradata events that are adjacent to "
    "another pageview on the same page will be deleted.",
    pageviews_proc[(pageviews_proc["has_events"] == False) &
(pageviews_proc["new_page"] == False)])

pageviews_proc = pageviews_proc[(pageviews_proc["has_events"] != False) |
(pageviews_proc["new_page"] != False)]

# Change identifiers to integers.
pageviews_proc["respondent_id"] = pageviews_proc["respondent_id"].astype(int)
pageviews_proc["page_id"] = pageviews_proc["page_id"].astype(int)
pageviews_proc["pageview_id"] = pageviews_proc["pageview_id"].astype(int)
pageviews_proc["recnum"] = pageviews_proc["recnum"].astype(int)

# Keep only relevant variables.
pageviews_proc = pageviews_proc[["pageview_id", "survey_id", "page_id", "respondent_id",
"recnum", "load_ts", "post_ts", "survey_lang",
    "uas", "browser_family", "browser_version", "os_family",
"os_version", "device_brand", "device_model",
    "touch_capable", "bot", "device_type", "pixel_ratio",
"screen_width", "screen_height", "screen_width_avail",
    "screen_height_avail", "viewport_width", "viewport_height",
"page_width", "page_height"]]

# %% RESPONSES PROCESSING
responses_proc = responses_raw.copy()

# Merge responses with page id and respondent id info.
responses_proc = pd.merge(responses_proc, pageviews_proc[["pageview_id", "page_id",
"respondent_id"]],
    on="pageview_id", how="left", indicator="pageviews_merge")

if (responses_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both").any():

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        processing_log.append(["responses_proc", "merging failure",
                               "Some response entries were not matched with pageviews
information.",
                               responses_proc[responses_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both"]])

# TODO: Question order information from metadata.

# Drop missing identifiers
# TODO: CHECK AND LOG!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
responses_proc = responses_proc[responses_proc["respondent_id"].notna()]

# Change identifiers to integers.
responses_proc["response_id"] = responses_proc["response_id"].astype(int)
responses_proc["pageview_id"] = responses_proc["pageview_id"].astype(int)
responses_proc["respondent_id"] = responses_proc["respondent_id"].astype(int)
responses_proc["page_id"] = responses_proc["page_id"].astype(int)
responses_proc["question_id"] = responses_proc["question_id"].astype(int)

# TODO NEKO IME, ĆE NI ITEM JE QUESTION a je sploh treba
responses_proc["item_name"] = np.where(responses_proc["item_name"].isna(),
responses_proc["question_name"], responses_proc["item_name"] )

# Keep only relevant variables.
responses_proc = responses_proc[["response_id", "pageview_id", "respondent_id", "page_id",
"response_ts", "question_id", "question_name",
                                "question_type", "question_input_type", "item_id",
"item_name", "response_option_id",
                                "response_option_unique_id", "response_option_code",
"response_action", "response_value"]]

# %% FOCUS CHANGES
focus_changes_proc = focus_changes_raw.copy()

# Add respondent and page ids.
focus_changes_proc = pd.merge(focus_changes_proc, pageviews_proc[["pageview_id",
"respondent_id", "page_id"]],
                               on="pageview_id", how="left", indicator="pageviews_merge")
if (focus_changes_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both").any():
    processing_log.append(["focus_changes_proc", "merging failure",
                            "Some focus change entries were not matched with pageviews.",
                            focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["pageviews_merge"] !=
"both"]])

# %% Study characteristics of events

# Time between page load and focus change event.
focus_changes_proc.sort_values(["respondent_id", "pageview_id", "focus_change_ts"],
inplace=True)
focus_changes_proc = pd.merge(focus_changes_proc, pageviews_proc[["pageview_id", "load_ts",
"browser_family", "browser_version",
                                                                    "os_family", "os_version",
"device_brand", "device_model"]],
                               on="pageview_id", how="left")
focus_changes_proc["load_time_diff"] = (focus_changes_proc["focus_change_ts"] -
focus_changes_proc["load_ts"]).dt.total_seconds()

# Number of focus and blur events by pageviews.
# This code can be run also later to check the effects of applied changes.
event_type_counts = focus_changes_proc.groupby(["pageview_id",
"change_type"]).agg(n_events=("focus_change_id", "count").reset_index()
event_type_counts = event_type_counts.pivot(index="pageview_id", columns="change_type")
event_type_counts.columns = ['_'.join(col).strip() for col in
event_type_counts.columns.values]
event_type_counts.reset_index(inplace=True)
pageviews_focus_events = pd.merge(pageviews_proc, event_type_counts, on="pageview_id",
how="left")
pageviews_focus_events["n_events_blur"].fillna(0, inplace=True)
pageviews_focus_events["n_events_focus"].fillna(0, inplace=True)
pageviews_focus_events["n_events_match"] = np.where((pageviews_focus_events["n_events_blur"] -
pageviews_focus_events["n_events_focus"]) == 0,
                                                    True, False)
pageviews_focus_events = pageviews_focus_events[["pageview_id", "respondent_id", "page_id",
"load_ts",
                                                    'n_events_blur', 'n_events_focus',
"n_events_match", "uas", "browser_family", "browser_version", "os_family", "os_version"]]

```

```

pageviews_focus_events.sort_values(['respondent_id', 'load_ts'], inplace=True)
del event_type_counts

# %% Remove identified "invalid" events
# It is not always clear which events are valid in terms of truly indicating that the
respondent left the survey window/tab. Only most
#

# Identify and remove events that (all deleted events are logged):
# - are recorded as occurred earlier than the corresponding page was loaded;
focus_changes_proc["flag_neg_time"] = np.where(focus_changes_proc["load_time_diff"] < 0, True,
False)
del_focus_events = focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["flag_neg_time"] == True]
focus_changes_proc = focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["flag_neg_time"] == False]

# - are focus events occurring less than 0.1 seconds after the page was loaded (some
browsers appear to trigger focus upon pageload);
focus_changes_proc["flag_focus_lt_100ms"] = np.where((focus_changes_proc["load_time_diff"] <
0.1) & (focus_changes_proc["change_type"] == "focus"),
True, False)
del_focus_events =
del_focus_events.append(focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["flag_focus_lt_100ms"] == True])
focus_changes_proc = focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["flag_focus_lt_100ms"] == False]

# - are repeated (i.e. two focus or blur events in row) events less than 0.1 second after
the same type of event;
focus_changes_proc.sort_values(["respondent_id", "pageview_id", "focus_change_ts"],
inplace=True)
focus_changes_proc["flag_repeated"] =
focus_changes_proc["change_type"].eq(focus_changes_proc["change_type"].shift(1))
focus_changes_proc.loc[focus_changes_proc["pageview_id"] !=
focus_changes_proc["pageview_id"].shift(1), "flag_repeated"] = False
focus_changes_proc["time_diff_repeated"] = focus_changes_proc.sort_values(
["respondent_id", "pageview_id",
"focus_change_ts"]).groupby('pageview_id')['focus_change_ts'].diff().dt.total_seconds()
focus_changes_proc["time_diff_repeated"] = np.where(focus_changes_proc["flag_repeated"] ==
True,
focus_changes_proc["time_diff_repeated"],
pd.NaT)
focus_changes_proc["flag_repeated_100ms"] = (focus_changes_proc["flag_repeated"] == True) &
(focus_changes_proc["time_diff_repeated"] < 0.1)
del_focus_events =
del_focus_events.append(focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["flag_repeated_100ms"] == True])
focus_changes_proc = focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["flag_repeated_100ms"] == False]

processing_log.append(["focus_changes_proc", "data deletion",
""
Focus change entries matching the following criteria were deleted:
- were recorded as occurred earlier than the corresponding page was loaded;
- were focus events occurring less than 0.1 seconds after the page was loaded;
- were repeated events less than 0.1 second after the same type of event;
"", del_focus_events])
del del_focus_events

# Drop missing identifiers
# TODO: CHECK AND LOG!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
focus_changes_proc = focus_changes_proc[focus_changes_proc["respondent_id"].notna()]

# Change identifiers to integers.
focus_changes_proc["focus_change_id"] = focus_changes_proc["focus_change_id"].astype(int)
focus_changes_proc["pageview_id"] = focus_changes_proc["pageview_id"].astype(int)
focus_changes_proc["respondent_id"] = focus_changes_proc["respondent_id"].astype(int)
focus_changes_proc["page_id"] = focus_changes_proc["page_id"].astype(int)

# Reorder and keep selected variables.
focus_changes_proc = focus_changes_proc[["focus_change_id", "pageview_id", "respondent_id",
"page_id", "focus_change_ts", "change_type"]]

# %% MESSAGES
messages_proc = messages_raw.copy()

# Add respondent and page ids.
messages_proc = pd.merge(messages_proc, pageviews_proc[["pageview_id", "respondent_id",
"page_id"]],
on="pageview_id", how="left", indicator="pageviews_merge")
if (messages_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both").any():

```

```

processing_log.append(["messages_proc", "merging failure",
                    "Some response message entries were not matched with pageviews.",
                    messages_proc[messages_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both"]])

# Merge messages with the same display_ts.
# TODO: Check here or during analysis whether any other events should be merged (e.g. due to
# very short time between two messages during
# the same pageview).
messages_proc["msg_group_id"] = messages_proc.groupby(["pageview_id", "msg_type",
"display_ts"]).groupby("pageview_id").groupby("msg_type").groupby("display_ts").grouper.group_info[0]
processing_log.append(["messages_proc", "note", "data aggregation",
                    "Message display entries with the same display_ts will be merged into a
single entry. Message IDs will be replaced. "
                    "The log contains a copy of full dataframe before this change is
applied.", messages_proc])
messages_proc["msg_id"] = messages_proc["msg_group_id"]
# We only list all trigger question names, not IDs, because question-level information is
pretty useless anyway. In the future, item-level
# info may be added.
messages_proc["trigger_question_names"] =
messages_proc.groupby("msg_id")["trigger_question_name"].transform(lambda x:
', '.join(x.astype(str)))
messages_proc.drop(columns=["trigger_question_id", "trigger_question_name", "msg_group_id"],
inplace=True)
# Only the record with the latest timestamp is kept.
messages_proc = messages_proc.sort_values(["msg_id",
"close_ts"]).groupby("msg_id").last().reset_index()

# Drop missing identifiers
# TODO: CHECK AND LOG!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
messages_proc = messages_proc[messages_proc["respondent_id"].notna()]

# Change identifiers to integers.
messages_proc["msg_id"] = messages_proc["msg_id"].astype(int)
messages_proc["pageview_id"] = messages_proc["pageview_id"].astype(int)
messages_proc["respondent_id"] = messages_proc["respondent_id"].astype(int)
messages_proc["page_id"] = messages_proc["page_id"].astype(int)

# Reorder and keep selected variables.
messages_proc = messages_proc[["msg_id", "pageview_id", "respondent_id", "page_id",
"display_ts", "close_ts", "msg_type",
                    "trigger_question_names", "ignorable", "msg_text",
"respondent_action"]]

# %% POINTER MOVEMENTS
pointer_proc = pointer_raw.copy()

# Calculate Euclidean distance to confirm zero-distance events.
pointer_proc["euclid_distance"] = np.sqrt((pointer_proc["end_coord_x"] -
pointer_proc["start_coord_x"])**2 + (
                    pointer_proc["end_coord_y"] -
pointer_proc["start_coord_y"])**2)

# Drop zero-distance events, but only if both Euclidean distance and move_distance are zero.
processing_log.append(["pointer_proc", "data deletion",
                    "Zero-distance pointer movement events will be removed if recorded andy
Euclidean distance are both zero.",
                    pointer_proc[(pointer_proc["move_distance"] == 0) &
(pointer_proc["euclid_distance"] == 0)])
pointer_proc = pointer_proc[(pointer_proc["move_distance"] != 0) |
(pointer_proc["euclid_distance"] != 0)]

# Problematic are only events where Euclidean distance is not zero and move_distance is zero.
It is possible - yet odd - that the Euclidean
# distance is zero if the movement starts and ends at the same point.
if ((pointer_proc["euclid_distance"] != 0) & (pointer_proc["move_distance"] == 0)).any():
    processing_log.append(["pointer_proc", "inconsistent data", "Some entries have non-zero
Euclidean distance but zero move distance.",
                    pointer_proc[(pointer_proc["euclid_distance"] != 0) &
(pointer_proc["move_distance"] == 0)])

# Add respondent and page ids.
pointer_proc = pd.merge(pointer_proc, pageviews_proc[["pageview_id", "respondent_id",
"page_id"]], on="pageview_id", how="left",
                    indicator="pageviews_merge")
if (pointer_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both").any():

```

```

        processing_log.append(["pointer_proc", "merging failure",
                              "Some response message entries were not matched with pageviews.",
                              pointer_proc[pointer_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both"]])

# Drop missing identifiers
# TODO: CHECK AND LOG!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
pointer_proc = pointer_proc[pointer_proc["respondent_id"].notna()]

# Change identifiers to integers.
pointer_proc["move_id"] = pointer_proc["move_id"].astype(int)
pointer_proc["pageview_id"] = pointer_proc["pageview_id"].astype(int)
pointer_proc["respondent_id"] = pointer_proc["respondent_id"].astype(int)
pointer_proc["page_id"] = pointer_proc["page_id"].astype(int)

# Reorder and keep selected variables.
pointer_proc = pointer_proc[["move_id", "pageview_id", "respondent_id", "page_id",
                             "move_start_ts", "move_end_ts",
                             "start_coord_x", "start_coord_y", "end_coord_x", "end_coord_y",
                             "move_distance"]]

# %% CLICKS
clicks_proc = clicks_raw.copy()

# Many click events seem to be recorded more than once. Identify clicks in which coordinate
change compared to the previous click.
clicks_proc.sort_values(["pageview_id", "click_ts"], inplace=True)
clicks_proc["diff_coord"] = np.where((clicks_proc["coord_x"].diff() == 0) &
                                     (clicks_proc["coord_y"].diff() == 0), False, True)
clicks_proc.loc[clicks_proc["pageview_id"] != clicks_proc["pageview_id"].shift(1),
               "diff_coord"] = True

# Time difference between events is used as further criterion to reduce errors in separating
click events. This may be improved in the
# future by analysing whether a group of click events refers to the same or different UI
elements.
# TODO: Recheck the logic behind merging events.
clicks_proc["same_coord_time_diff"] = clicks_proc.sort_values(["pageview_id",
                                                             "click_ts"])["click_ts"].diff().dt.total_seconds()
clicks_proc.loc[clicks_proc["pageview_id"] != clicks_proc["pageview_id"].shift(1),
               "same_coord_time_diff"] = np.NaN
clicks_proc["base_event"] = np.where((clicks_proc["diff_coord"] == False) &
                                     (clicks_proc["same_coord_time_diff"] < 0.1 ), False, True)

# Give the same identifier to all sequential clicks designated for merging. This is done by
removing identifiers for such events
# then forward filling the ID of the first click event.
clicks_proc["click_id"] = clicks_proc["click_id"] * clicks_proc["base_event"]
clicks_proc["click_id"].replace(0, np.nan, inplace=True)
clicks_proc["click_id"].fillna(method="ffill", inplace=True)

# TODO: Currently we just remove all non-base events without even logging themn.
# This needs to be changed to pivoting that will enable analysis of event types.
clicks_proc = clicks_proc[clicks_proc["base_event"] == True]

# # Define new IDs based on groups of events
# clicks_proc["click_group_id"] = np.where(clicks_proc["same_coord"] == True,
# clicks_proc["click_id"].shift(1), clicks_proc["click_id"])
# clicks_proc["click_group_id"] = clicks_proc["click_group_id"].rank(method="dense")

# # Sequentially count the number of click events in each group (the number is increased by
one to get the total number of events in group).
# clicks_proc["count"] = clicks_proc.sort_values(["pageview_id",
"click_ts"]).groupby("click_group_id")["click_group_id"].cumcount()
# clicks_proc["count"] += 1
# # More than two events grouped together is unexpected and should be handled. Errors will not
necessarily occur, but it should be checked
# # anyway.
# if clicks_proc["count"].max() > 2:
#     processing_log.append(["clicks_proc", "unexpected data",
#                             "Some groups of click events contain more than two entries, wich
can cause unexpected results. Adapt procedures if needed",
#                             clicks_proc[clicks_proc["count"] > 2]])

# # Merge click events ccurring next to each other with the same coordinates. The earliest
timestamp and all div-related info is retained.

```

```

# processing_log.append(["clicks_proc", "note", "data aggregation",
# "Click events occurring next to each other with the same coordinates
will be merged into a single entry. "
# "Click IDs will be replaced. The log contains a copy of full
dataframe before this change is applied.",
# clicks_proc])

# # Use the first event timestamp and replace original click IDs with group IDs.
# clicks_proc["click_ts"] = clicks_proc.sort_values(["pageview_id",
"click_ts"]).groupby("click_group_id")["click_ts"].transform("first")
# clicks_proc["click_id"] = clicks_proc["click_group_id"]

# grouped_clicks = clicks_proc.pivot(index="click_id",
# columns="count",
# values=["div_id", "div_class", "div_type", "same_coord"])

# Add respondent and page ids.
clicks_proc = pd.merge(clicks_proc, pageviews_proc[["pageview_id", "respondent_id",
"page_id"]], on="pageview_id", how="left",
indicator="pageviews_merge")
if (clicks_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both").any():
    processing_log.append(["clicks_proc", "merging failure",
"Some click entries were not matched with pageviews.",
clicks_proc[clicks_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both"]])

# Drop missing identifiers
# TODO: CHECK AND LOG!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
clicks_proc = clicks_proc[clicks_proc["respondent_id"].notna()]

# Change identifiers to integers.
clicks_proc["click_id"] = clicks_proc["click_id"].astype(int)
clicks_proc["pageview_id"] = clicks_proc["pageview_id"].astype(int)
clicks_proc["respondent_id"] = clicks_proc["respondent_id"].astype(int)
clicks_proc["page_id"] = clicks_proc["page_id"].astype(int)

# Reorder and keep selected variables.
clicks_proc = clicks_proc[["click_id", "pageview_id", "respondent_id", "page_id", "click_ts",
"coord_x", "coord_y"]]

%% VIEW CHANGES
# TODO: This for now only includes orientation changes, everything else is dropped.
view_changes_proc = view_changes_raw[view_changes_raw["change_type"] == "orientation_change"]

# Add respondent and page ids.
view_changes_proc = pd.merge(view_changes_proc, pageviews_proc[["pageview_id",
"respondent_id", "page_id"]], on="pageview_id", how="left",
indicator="pageviews_merge")
if (view_changes_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both").any():
    processing_log.append(["view_changes_proc", "merging failure",
"Some view changes entries were not matched with pageviews.",
view_changes_proc[view_changes_proc["pageviews_merge"] != "both"]])

# %% EVENTS LIST
# Processed events list excludes events that were excluded during processing of individual
datasets.

# - pointer_move_start and pointer_move_end (between the two events is active period that
should be considered).

```

2.4 Basic analysis

```

# TODO: Imena pomoÅ¾nih objektov za agregacijo naj bodo konsistentna. Glej npr. za pointer kot
primer.

```

```

# %% SETUP

```

```

settings["results_folder"] = "/Users/nejc/WD/Python/Paradata/"
settings["use_common_names"] = True
settings["export_to_excel"] = False

```

```

# %% SOME HELPER STUFF

```

```

# Matching recnums and respondent ids.

```

```

ref_recnum_id = pageviews_proc.groupby(["respondent_id", "recnum"]).size().reset_index()
ref_recnum_id.drop(columns=0, inplace=True)

# Matching item IDs and names.
ref_item_names = responses_proc.groupby(["page_id", "item_id",
"item_name"]).size().reset_index()
ref_item_names = pd.merge(ref_item_names, survey_metadata["pages"][["page_id", "page_seq"]],
on="page_id", how="left")
ref_item_names.drop(columns=0, inplace=True)

# Matching question IDs and names.
ref_question_names = responses_proc.groupby(["question_id",
"question_name"]).size().reset_index()
ref_question_names.drop(columns=0, inplace=True)

# Rules for common item names (i.e. due to having experimental versions of items).
ref_item_versions = pd.read_csv(settings["item_versions_file"])
ref_common_item_names = pd.melt(ref_item_versions, id_vars=["common_name"],
value_vars=["version_1", "version_2", "version_3",
"version_4", "version_5"], value_name="item name")
ref_common_item_names.drop(columns="variable", inplace=True)

# %% FOCUS OUTS
focus_out_analysis = focus_changes_proc.copy()

#
focus_out_analysis.sort_values(["respondent_id", "pageview_id", "focus_change_id"],
inplace=True)

# For sequentially equal events during the same pageview we take the latest event for blur and
the earliest event for focus.
# We do this by setting equal ID to all sequentially equal events, then taking the first or
the last event in the group depending on
# the type.
focus_out_analysis["seq_equal"] = np.where((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] ==
focus_out_analysis["change_type"].shift(1)) & (focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"] ==
focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"].shift(1)), True, False)
focus_out_analysis["focus_change_id"] = np.where(focus_out_analysis["seq_equal"] == True,
np.nan, focus_out_analysis["focus_change_id"])
focus_out_analysis["focus_change_id"].fillna(method="ffill", inplace=True)
focus_out_analysis["seq_min_ts"] =
focus_out_analysis.groupby("focus_change_id")["focus_change_ts"].transform("min")
focus_out_analysis["seq_max_ts"] =
focus_out_analysis.groupby("focus_change_id")["focus_change_ts"].transform("max")
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] == "focus") &
(focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"] ==
focus_out_analysis["seq_min_ts"])) |
((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] == "blur") &
(focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"] ==
focus_out_analysis["seq_max_ts"]))]

# Duration of focus out event. Only relevant are durations calculated from previous blur to
the next focus. The code above eliminates all
# sequential repeated events on the same page, therefore focus event will be preceded on the
page by blur event. However, if focus event is
# the first on the page, then duration is not valid and will be missing.
focus_out_analysis["duration"] =
focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"].diff().dt.total_seconds()
focus_out_analysis["focus_out_ts"] = focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"].shift(1)
focus_out_analysis["duration"] = np.where((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] == "blur") |
(focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"] !=
focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"].shift(1)),
np.nan, focus_out_analysis["duration"])

# TODO: Preveri od kod negativna trajanja, tule jih damo samo na nič. Tule tudi odstranimo
primerke na zadnji strani,
# ker drugače nagajajo adjusted časi. Premisli ponovno!
focus_out_analysis["duration"] = np.where(focus_out_analysis["duration"] < 0, 0,
focus_out_analysis["duration"])
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[focus_out_analysis["page_id"] != -2]

# Keep only focus events with valid duration.

```

```

# TODO: Log deleted entries.
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[focus_out_analysis["duration"].notna()]
focus_out_analysis["duration_geq_5s"] = np.where(focus_out_analysis["duration"] >= 5, True,
False)

focus_out_analysis.rename(columns={"focus_change_ts": "focus_in_ts"}, inplace=True)
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[["focus_change_id", "pageview_id", "respondent_id",
"page_id", "focus_in_ts",
"focus_out_ts", "duration", "duration_geq_5s"]]

# Aggregate focus events at the respondent level and calculate adjusted pageview times. This
is used later to calculate adjusted pageview
# times.
respondent_focus_pageview = focus_out_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id",
"pageview_id"]).agg(n_focus_out=("focus_change_id", "count"),

n_focus_out_5s=("duration_geq_5s", "sum"),

focus_out_duration=("duration", "sum")).reset_index()

# Aggregation at the page level and calculation of adjusted page
respondent_focus_page = focus_out_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id",
"page_id"]).agg(n_focus_out=("focus_change_id", "count"),

n_focus_out_5s=("duration_geq_5s", "sum"),

focus_out_duration=("duration", "sum")).reset_index()

# Aggregation at the respondent level.
respondent_focus_out_sum =
focus_out_analysis.groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_focus_out=("focus_change_id", "count"),

n_focus_out_5s=("duration_geq_5s", "sum"),

focus_out_duration=("duration", "sum")).reset_index()

# Add page order.
respondent_focus_page = pd.merge(respondent_focus_page, survey_metadata["pages"][["page_id",
"page_seq"]], on="page_id", how="left")
respondent_focus_page.sort_values("page_seq", inplace=True)

# Results table.
focus_out_results = respondent_focus_page.pivot(index="respondent_id", columns="page_seq",
values=["n_focus_out", "n_focus_out_5s",

"focus_out_duration"])
focus_out_results.columns = [tup[0] + "_p" + str(tup[1]) for tup in
focus_out_results.columns.values]
focus_out_results.reset_index(inplace=True)
focus_out_results = pd.merge(respondent_focus_out_sum, focus_out_results, on="respondent_id")
focus_out_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]], focus_out_results,
on="respondent_id")

# Export to Excel
if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    focus_out_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "focus_out_respondent_level.xlsx",
index=False)

# %% PAGEVIEWS AND FOCUS OUTS
# We do this together to exchange information between the two tables on the fly. It is a bit
of a mess, though.
pageviews_analysis = pageviews_proc.copy()
focus_out_analysis = focus_changes_proc.copy()

# %% Pageviews duration

# Sort values by respondent and timestamp.
pageviews_analysis.sort_values(['respondent_id', 'load_ts'], inplace=True)

# Pageviews duration and pageview end estimate (which is simply adding duration to load_ts to
get next pageview load ts to the same row).
pageviews_analysis["pview_dur"] = pageviews_analysis.sort_values(

```

```

    ['respondent_id', 'load_ts']).groupby('respondent_id')['load_ts'].diff(-
1).dt.total_seconds()*(-1)
pageviews_analysis["end_ts"] = pageviews_analysis["load_ts"] +
pd.to_timedelta(pageviews_analysis["pview_dur"], unit="s")

# %% Focus outs
focus_out_analysis = pd.merge(focus_out_analysis, pageviews_analysis[["pageview_id",
"load_ts", "end_ts"]], on="pageview_id", how="left")
focus_out_analysis["event_outside_ts"] = np.where((focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"] <
focus_out_analysis["load_ts"]) |
                                                    (focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"] >
focus_out_analysis["end_ts"]), True, False)
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[focus_out_analysis["event_outside_ts"] == False]

# For sequentially equal events during the same pageview we take the latest event for blur and
the earliest event for focus.
# We do this by setting equal ID to all sequentially equal events, then taking the first or
the last event in the group depending on
# the type.
focus_out_analysis.sort_values(["respondent_id", "pageview_id", "focus_change_id"],
inplace=True)
focus_out_analysis["seq_equal"] = np.where((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] ==
focus_out_analysis["change_type"].shift(1)) & (focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"] ==
focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"].shift(1)), True, False)
focus_out_analysis["focus_change_id"] = np.where(focus_out_analysis["seq_equal"] == True,
np.nan, focus_out_analysis["focus_change_id"])
focus_out_analysis["focus_change_id"].fillna(method="ffill", inplace=True)
focus_out_analysis["seq_min_ts"] =
focus_out_analysis.groupby("focus_change_id")["focus_change_ts"].transform("min")
focus_out_analysis["seq_max_ts"] =
focus_out_analysis.groupby("focus_change_id")["focus_change_ts"].transform("max")
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] == "focus") &
(focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"] ==
focus_out_analysis["seq_min_ts"])) |
                                         ((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] == "blur") &
(focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"] ==
focus_out_analysis["seq_max_ts"]))]

# Duration of focus out event. Only relevant are durations calculated from previous blur to
the next focus. The code above eliminates all
# sequential repeated events on the same page, therefore focus event will be preceded on the
page by blur event. However, if focus event is
# the first on the page, then duration is not valid and will be missing.
focus_out_analysis["duration"] =
focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"].diff().dt.total_seconds()
focus_out_analysis["focus_out_ts"] = focus_out_analysis["focus_change_ts"].shift(1)
focus_out_analysis["duration"] = np.where((focus_out_analysis["change_type"] == "blur") |
(focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"] !=
focus_out_analysis["pageview_id"].shift(1)),
np.nan, focus_out_analysis["duration"])

# TODO: Preveri od kod negativna trajanja, tule jih damo samo na nič. Tule tudi odstranimo
primerke na zadnji strani,
# ker drugače nagajajo adjusted časi. Premisli ponovnoi
focus_out_analysis["duration"] = np.where(focus_out_analysis["duration"] < 0, 0,
focus_out_analysis["duration"])
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[focus_out_analysis["page_id"] != -2]

# Keep only focus events with valid duration.
# TODO: Log deleted entries.
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[focus_out_analysis["duration"].notna()]
focus_out_analysis["duration_geq_5s"] = np.where(focus_out_analysis["duration"] >= 5, True,
False)

focus_out_analysis.rename(columns={"focus_change_ts": "focus_in_ts"}, inplace=True)
focus_out_analysis = focus_out_analysis[["focus_change_id", "pageview_id", "respondent_id",
"page_id", "focus_in_ts",
                                         "focus_out_ts", "duration", "duration_geq_5s"]]

# Aggregate focus events at the respondent level and calculate adjusted pageview times. This
is used later to calculate adjusted pageview
# times.
respondent_focus_pageview = focus_out_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id",
"pageview_id"]).agg(n_focus_out=("focus_change_id", "count"),

```

```

n_focus_out_5s=("duration_geq_5s", "sum"),

focus_out_duration=("duration", "sum").reset_index()

# Aggregation at the page level and calculation of adjusted page
respondent_focus_page = focus_out_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id",
"page_id"]).agg(n_focus_out=("focus_change_id", "count"),

n_focus_out_5s=("duration_geq_5s", "sum"),

focus_out_duration=("duration", "sum").reset_index()

# Aggregation at the respondent level.
respondent_focus_out_sum =
focus_out_analysis.groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_focus_out=("focus_change_id", "count"),

n_focus_out_5s=("duration_geq_5s", "sum"),

focus_out_duration=("duration", "sum").reset_index()

# Add page order.
respondent_focus_page = pd.merge(respondent_focus_page, survey_metadata["pages"][["page_id",
"page_seq"]], on="page_id", how="left")
respondent_focus_page.sort_values("page_seq", inplace=True)

# Results table.
focus_out_results = respondent_focus_page.pivot(index="respondent_id", columns="page_seq",
values=["n_focus_out", "n_focus_out_5s",

"focus_out_duration"])
focus_out_results.columns = [tup[0] + "_p" + str(tup[1]) for tup in
focus_out_results.columns.values]
focus_out_results.reset_index(inplace=True)
focus_out_results = pd.merge(respondent_focus_out_sum, focus_out_results, on="respondent_id")
focus_out_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]], focus_out_results,
on="respondent_id")

# Export to Excel
if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    focus_out_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "focus_out_respondent_level.xlsx",
index=False)

# %% Further processing of pageviews.
# Pageviews duration adjusted for focus out.
pageviews_analysis = pd.merge(pageviews_analysis, respondent_focus_pageview[["pageview_id",
"focus_out_duration"]], on="pageview_id", how="left")
pageviews_analysis["focus_out_duration"].fillna(value=0, inplace=True)
pageviews_analysis["pview_dur_foc"] = pageviews_analysis["pview_dur"] -
pageviews_analysis["focus_out_duration"]

# Number of pageviews and duration of the first and total pageviews. Total pageviews count
includes page visits and pageviews that are
# not the result of page changes (e.g. refreshes, but also potential "ghost" pageviews that
have not been filtered out
# during the data processing).
respondent_pageviews = pageviews_analysis.sort_values(['respondent_id', 'load_ts']).groupby(
["respondent_id", "page_id"]).agg(n_pageviews=("pageview_id", "count"),
duration_1st_pageview=("pview_dur", "first"),
dur_tot=("pview_dur", "sum"),
duration_1st_pageview_foc=("pview_dur_foc", "first"),
dur_tot_foc=("pview_dur_foc", "sum")).reset_index()
respondent_pageviews["dur_tot"] = np.where(respondent_pageviews["dur_tot"] == 0, np.nan,
respondent_pageviews["dur_tot"])
respondent_pageviews["dur_tot_foc"] = np.where(respondent_pageviews["dur_tot_foc"] == 0,
np.nan,
respondent_pageviews["dur_tot_foc"])

# Page visits.
# Check whether the pageview refers to a page that is different to previous (i.e. pageview
event due to moving to a
# different page) and assign same visit_id if not # Type conversion to bool uses the fact that
bool(np.nan) = True.
# TODO: Calculate time of the first VISIT.
pageviews_analysis.sort_values(['respondent_id', 'load_ts'], inplace=True)

```

```

pageviews_analysis["new_visit"] =
pageviews_analysis.groupby('respondent_id')['page_id'].diff().astype(bool)
pageviews_analysis["visit_id"] = pageviews_analysis["pageview_id"] *
pageviews_analysis["new_visit"]
pageviews_analysis["visit_id"].replace(0, np.nan, inplace=True)
pageviews_analysis["visit_id"].fillna(method="ffill", inplace=True)

# Calculate duration of individual visits as the sum of pageviews durations belonging to the
same visit.
visits_analysis = pageviews_analysis[["pageview_id", "visit_id", "page_id", "respondent_id",
"new_visit", "load_ts", "pview_dur",
"pview_dur_foc"]].copy()
visits_analysis["vis_dur"] = visits_analysis.groupby(["visit_id"])["pview_dur"].transform(sum)
visits_analysis["vis_dur_foc"] =
visits_analysis.groupby(["visit_id"])["pview_dur_foc"].transform(sum)
visits_analysis = visits_analysis[visits_analysis["new_visit"] == True]
visits_analysis["vis_dur_foc"] = np.where(visits_analysis["vis_dur_foc"] == 0, np.nan,
visits_analysis["vis_dur_foc"])
visits_analysis["vis_dur"] = np.where(visits_analysis["vis_dur"] == 0, np.nan,
visits_analysis["vis_dur"])
visits_analysis.sort_values(['respondent_id', 'load_ts'], inplace=True)

# Respondent-level statistics of visits.
visits_analysis.sort_values(['respondent_id', 'load_ts'], inplace=True)
respondent_visits = visits_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id",
"page_id"]).agg(n_p_visits=("visit_id", "count"),

dur_vis1=("vis_dur", "first"),

dur_vis1_foc=("vis_dur_foc", "first").reset_index()
respondent_visits["dur_vis1"] = np.where(respondent_visits["dur_vis1"] == 0, np.nan,
respondent_visits["dur_vis1"])
respondent_visits["dur_vis1_foc"] = np.where(respondent_visits["dur_vis1_foc"] == 0, np.nan,
respondent_visits["dur_vis1_foc"])
respondent_visits["multiple_page_visits"] = np.where(respondent_visits["n_p_visits"] > 1,
True, False)

# Merge with pageviews.
respondent_pageviews = pd.merge(respondent_pageviews, respondent_visits, on=["respondent_id",
"page_id"])

# Device onfo.
# TODO: UAS-based info currently uses the first value. Because there are some instances of
unexplained UAS changes across pageviews,
# more informed decision about which info to keep should be developed.
respondent_device = pageviews_analysis.groupby("respondent_id").agg(
device_type=("device_type", "first"),

browser_family=("browser_family", "first"),

browser_version=("browser_version", "first"),

os_family=("os_family", "first"),

os_version=("os_version", "first"),

device_brand=("device_brand", "first"),

device_model=("device_model", "first"),

touch_capable=("touch_capable", "first").reset_index()

respondent_pageviews_sum =
respondent_pageviews.groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_pageviews=("n_pageviews", "sum"),
n_p_visits=("n_p_visits", "sum"),
n_visited_pages=("page_id",
"nunique"),
dur_tot=("dur_tot", "sum"),
dur_tot_foc=("dur_tot_foc", "sum"))

respondent_pageviews_sum = pd.merge(respondent_pageviews_sum, respondent_device,
on="respondent_id")

# Number of pages with multiple visits.

```

```

respondent_visits_sum = respondent_visits[respondent_visits["multiple_page_visits"] ==
True].groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_mult_vis_p=("page_id", "nunique")).reset_index()
respondent_pageviews_sum = pd.merge(respondent_pageviews_sum, respondent_visits_sum,
on="respondent_id", how="left")
respondent_pageviews_sum["n_mult_vis_p"] = respondent_pageviews_sum["n_mult_vis_p"].fillna(0)
del respondent_visits_sum

# Add page order.
respondent_pageviews = pd.merge(respondent_pageviews, survey_metadata["pages"][["page_id",
"page_seq"]], on="page_id", how="left")
respondent_pageviews.sort_values("page_seq", inplace=True)

# Results table.
pageviews_results = respondent_pageviews.pivot(index="respondent_id", columns="page_seq",
values=["n_pageviews", "dur_vis1",
"dur_vis1_foc",
"dur_tot_foc", "dur_tot",
"n_p_visits"])
pageviews_results.columns = [tup[0] + "_p" + str(tup[1]) for tup in
pageviews_results.columns.values]
pageviews_results.reset_index(inplace=True)
pageviews_results = pd.merge(respondent_pageviews_sum, pageviews_results, on="respondent_id")
pageviews_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]], pageviews_results,
on="respondent_id")

# Export results to Excel.
if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    pageviews_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "pageviews_respondent_level.xlsx",
index=False)

# %% RESPONSES
responses_analysis = responses_proc.copy()

# %% Response times for individual items

# Append tables of pageviews and responses to calculate response times.
# TODO: Popravi za primere, ko ne obstaja text_leave vnos, ki ga zdaj uporabljaÅ; kot Å□as
odgovora na odprto vpraÅ;anje
#check.sort_values(["respondent_id", "pageview_id", "response_ts"], inplace=True)
#check["flag_repeated"] = check["response_action"].eq(check["response_action"].shift(1))
#check.loc[check["item_name"] != check["item_name"].shift(1), "flag_repeated"] = False

response_times_analysis = pd.concat([pageviews_proc[["pageview_id", "respondent_id",
"load_ts"]],
responses_proc[["response_id", "respondent_id", "pageview_id",
"response_ts", "item_name", "response_action"]]])

# We drop text field entry events here.
# TODO: Calculate time between entering and leaving the text field before dropping.
response_times_analysis = response_times_analysis[(response_times_analysis["response_action"]
!= "text_enter")]

response_times_analysis["event_type"] = np.where(response_times_analysis["load_ts"].notna(),
"pageview", np.nan)
response_times_analysis["event_ts"] = np.where(response_times_analysis["load_ts"].notna(),
response_times_analysis["load_ts"], pd.NaT)

response_times_analysis["event_type"] =
np.where(response_times_analysis["response_ts"].notna(), "response",
response_times_analysis["event_type"])
response_times_analysis["event_ts"] = np.where(response_times_analysis["response_ts"].notna(),
response_times_analysis["response_ts"], response_times_analysis["event_ts"])

response_times_analysis["event_ts"] =
response_times_analysis["event_ts"].astype(np.datetime64)

response_times_analysis = response_times_analysis[["response_id", "pageview_id",
"respondent_id", "event_type", "event_ts", "item_name", "response_action"]]
response_times_analysis.sort_values(["respondent_id", "event_ts"], inplace=True)

# Calculate response times as the difference between two consecutive events.
response_times_analysis.reset_index(inplace=True)
response_times_analysis["response_time"] =
response_times_analysis.sort_values(["respondent_id", "event_ts"]).groupby(["respondent_id"])["
event_ts"].diff().dt.total_seconds()

```

```

response_times_analysis = response_times_analysis[response_times_analysis["event_type"] !=
"pageview"]

# Merge data to the responses dataframe and list items with missing response times.
responses_analysis = pd.merge(responses_analysis, response_times_analysis[["response_id",
"response_time"]], how="left", on="response_id",
                             indicator="response_times_merge")
missing_response_times = responses_analysis[(responses_analysis["response_times_merge"] ==
"left_only") &
                                             (responses_analysis["response_action"] !=
"text_enter")]

if not missing_response_times.empty:
    processing_log.append(["responses_analysis", "medium", "missing data",
                          "Some response entries do not have valid calculated response
time.", missing_response_times])

del missing_response_times

# Results
# TODO: Check that item ID and item name are truly unique combinations and rethink if both are
needed and are OK for grouping.
# TODO: KakÅen je rezultat suma, Åie je ena izmed seÅitetih vrednosti missing?
respondent_item_responses = responses_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id", "item_name",
"item_id"]).agg(n_responses=("item_id", "count"),

response_time_first=("response_time", "first"),

response_time_total=("response_time", "sum")).reset_index()

respondent_item_responses["response_time_total"] =
np.where(respondent_item_responses["response_time_total"] == 0,
        np.nan,
respondent_item_responses["response_time_total"])
respondent_item_responses["response_time_first"] =
np.where(respondent_item_responses["response_time_first"] == 0,
        np.nan,
respondent_item_responses["response_time_first"])

# Number of response changes derived simply by subtracting 1 from the number of responses to
each item. (Each subsequent response to an
# item counts as a change.)
respondent_item_responses["n_response_changes"] = respondent_item_responses["n_responses"] - 1
respondent_item_responses["changed_response"] =
np.where(respondent_item_responses["n_response_changes"] > 0, True, False)

# Aggregated results at the respondent level.
respondent_responses_sum =
respondent_item_responses.groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_responses=("n_responses", "sum"),

n_response_changes=("n_response_changes", "sum"),

n_response_change_items=("changed_response", "sum")).reset_index()
# Replace item names with common names if specified.
# if settings["use_common_names"]:
#     respondent_item_responses["original_name"] = respondent_item_responses["item_name"]
#     for index, i_item in ref_common_item_names.iterrows():
#         respondent_item_responses["item_name"] =
np.where(respondent_item_responses["item_name"] == i_item["item_name"],
        i_item["common_name"],
#
#
respondent_item_responses["item_name"])
# del i_item
# del index

# Prepare results
responses_results = respondent_item_responses.pivot(index="respondent_id",
columns="item_name", values=["n_responses", "response_time_first", "response_time_total"])
responses_results.columns = ['_'.join(col).strip() for col in
responses_results.columns.values]
responses_results.reset_index(inplace=True)
responses_results = pd.merge(respondent_responses_sum, responses_results, on="respondent_id")
responses_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]], responses_results,
on="respondent_id")

# Export results to Excel.

```

```

if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    responses_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "responses_respondent_level.xlsx",
index=False)

# %% POINTER MOVEMENTS
pointer_analysis = pointer_proc.copy()

# Move duration and speed.
# TODO: Not sure if move speed really makes sense, eespecially with aggregations at the level
of page or respondent.
pointer_analysis["move_duration"] = (pointer_analysis["move_end_ts"] -
pointer_analysis["move_start_ts"]).dt.total_seconds()
pointer_analysis["move_speed"] = pointer_analysis["move_distance"] /
pointer_analysis["move_duration"]

### Respondent-level
# Aggregation at the page level.
respondent_pointer_page = pointer_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id",
"page_id"]).agg(move_duration=("move_duration", "sum"),

move_distance=("move_distance", "sum")).reset_index()
respondent_pointer_page["move_speed"] = respondent_pointer_page["move_distance"] /
respondent_pointer_page["move_duration"]

# Aggregation at the respondent level.
respondent_pointer_sum =
pointer_analysis.groupby("respondent_id").agg(move_dur_tot=("move_duration", "sum"),

move_distance_total=("move_distance", "sum")).reset_index()
respondent_pointer_sum["move_speed_total"] = respondent_pointer_sum["move_distance_total"] /
respondent_pointer_sum["move_dur_tot"]

# Add page order.
respondent_pointer_page = pd.merge(respondent_pointer_page,
survey_metadata["pages"][["page_id", "page_seq"]], on="page_id", how="left")
respondent_pointer_page.sort_values("page_seq", inplace=True)

# Results table.
pointer_results = respondent_pointer_page.pivot(index="respondent_id", columns="page_seq",
values=["move_duration", "move_distance", "move_speed"])
pointer_results.columns = [tup[0] + "_p" + str(tup[1]) for tup in
pointer_results.columns.values]
pointer_results.reset_index(inplace=True)
pointer_results = pd.merge(respondent_pointer_sum, pointer_results, on="respondent_id")
pointer_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]], pointer_results,
on="respondent_id")

# Export to Excel
if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    pointer_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] +
"pointer_movement_respondent_level.xlsx", index=False)

# %% CLICKS
clicks_analysis = clicks_proc.copy()

### Respondent-level
# Aggregation at the page level.
respondent_clicks_page = clicks_analysis.groupby(["respondent_id",
"page_id"]).agg(n_clicks=("click_id", "count")).reset_index()

# Aggregation at the respondent level.
respondent_clicks_sum = clicks_analysis.groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_clicks=("click_id",
"count")).reset_index()

# Add page order.
respondent_clicks_page = pd.merge(respondent_clicks_page, survey_metadata["pages"][["page_id",
"page_seq"]], on="page_id", how="left")
respondent_clicks_page.sort_values("page_seq", inplace=True)

# Results table.
clicks_results = respondent_clicks_page.pivot(index="respondent_id", columns="page_seq",
values=["n_clicks"])
clicks_results.columns = [tup[0] + "_p" + str(tup[1]) for tup in
clicks_results.columns.values]
clicks_results.reset_index(inplace=True)

```

```

clicks_results = pd.merge(respondent_clicks_sum, clicks_results, on="respondent_id")
clicks_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]], clicks_results,
on="respondent_id")

# Export to Excel
if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    clicks_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "clicks_respondent_level.xlsx",
index=False)

# %% MESSAGES
messages_analysis = messages_proc.copy()

### Respondent-level

# Aggregation at the respondent level.
respondent_messages_sum = messages_analysis.groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_messages=("msg_id",
"count")).reset_index()
respondent_inr_messages_sum = messages_analysis[messages_analysis["msg_type"] ==
"item_nonresponse"].groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_inr_messages=("msg_id",
"count")).reset_index()
respondent_messages_sum = pd.merge(respondent_messages_sum, respondent_inr_messages_sum,
how="left", on="respondent_id")
del respondent_inr_messages_sum

# Results
messages_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]],
respondent_messages_sum, on="respondent_id")

# Export to Excel
if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    messages_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "messages_respondent_level.xlsx",
index=False)

# %% VIEW CHANGES
# TODO: This only analyses orientation changes, it needs to be completely rewritten to account
for other view change events.
view_changes_analysis = view_changes_proc.copy()
respondent_view_changes_sum =
view_changes_analysis.groupby("respondent_id").agg(n_orient_change_pages=("page_id",
"nunique")).reset_index()
view_changes_results = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]],
respondent_view_changes_sum, on="respondent_id")

if settings["export_to_excel"]:
    view_changes_results.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] +
"view_changes_respondent_level.xlsx", index=False)

# %% SUMMARY EXPORTS

# Aggregations at the respondent level.
respondent_level_sum = pd.merge(ref_recnum_id[["respondent_id", "recnum"]],
respondent_pageviews_sum, on="respondent_id")
respondent_level_sum = pd.merge(respondent_level_sum, respondent_responses_sum,
on="respondent_id", how="outer")
respondent_level_sum = pd.merge(respondent_level_sum, respondent_messages_sum,
on="respondent_id", how="outer")
respondent_level_sum = pd.merge(respondent_level_sum, respondent_clicks_sum,
on="respondent_id", how="outer")
respondent_level_sum = pd.merge(respondent_level_sum, respondent_pointer_sum,
on="respondent_id", how="outer")
respondent_level_sum = pd.merge(respondent_level_sum, respondent_view_changes_sum,
on="respondent_id", how="outer")
respondent_level_sum = pd.merge(respondent_level_sum, respondent_focus_out_sum,
on="respondent_id", how="outer")
respondent_level_sum.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "respondent_level_sum.xlsx",
index=False)
ref_item_names.to_excel(settings["results_folder"] + "ref_item_names.xlsx", index=False)

del respondent_pageviews
del respondent_visits
del respondent_pageviews_sum

```